

Prediction of paperboard properties and their variability based on raw material and process data

Vorhersage von Kartoneigenschaften und deren Variabilität auf der Grundlage von Rohstoff- und Prozessdaten

Master thesis by Rosario Othen

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1. Review: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Samuel Schabel

2. Review: Tekn. Dr. Hannes Vomhoff

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UNIVERSITÄT
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Papierfabrikation und
Mechanische
Verfahrenstechnik

Name: Rosario Othen

Student ID: 2855554

Course of studies: M.Sc. Paper Science and Technology – Papiertechnik und biobasierte Faserwerkstoffe

Master thesis No. 96

Supervisor: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Samuel Schabel, Tekn. Dr. Hannes Vomhoff

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Samuel Schabel

Fachgebiet Papierfabrikation und Mechanische Verfahrenstechnik

Technische Universität Darmstadt

Alexanderstraße 8

64283 Darmstadt

Tekn. Dr. Hannes Vomhoff

Senior Research Manager

Holmen AB

Strandvägen 1

114 51 Stockholm

Master-Thesis Nr. 96

für

Rosario Othen, Matrikel-Nr. 2855554

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
DARMSTADT

Thema: Vorhersage von Kartoneigenschaften und deren Variabilität auf der Grundlage von Rohstoff- und Prozessdaten

Prediction of paperboard properties and their variability based on raw material and process data

Der Kartonherstellungsprozess ist ein sehr komplexer Prozess mit vielen Eingabeparametern. Darüber hinaus variieren auch die Eigenschaften des eingehenden Rohmaterials. Es ist daher schwierig, die Eigenschaften des Endproduktes quantitativ vorherzusagen. Mit der Weiterentwicklung und dem wesentlich einfacheren Zugang zu überwachten maschinellen Lernmethoden in den letzten Jahren, stehen jedoch neue leistungsfähige Möglichkeiten zur Verfügung. Das Ziel der vorliegenden Arbeit ist es, einige dieser Methoden zu implementieren und zu evaluieren, um die wichtigsten Produkteigenschaften (Dicke, Biegesteifigkeit, Rollneigung, Verdrehung) für eine reale industrielle Kartonmaschine und ihre Variabilität (z.B. ausgedrückt als Standardabweichung) auf der Grundlage von Daten vorherzusagen, die aus Prozessdaten gewonnen wurden (z.B. Fasermorphologie, Stoffzusammensetzung, Stoffbehandlung, Stoffkonzentration, Differenz zwischen Strahl- und Siebgeschwindigkeit, Faserorientierungsprofil). Dieses Modell wird dann zur Identifizierung der empfindlichsten Prozessstufe(n) in Bezug auf die Variation der Produkteigenschaften verwendet.

The paperboard production process is a very complex process with many input parameters. In addition, the properties of the ingoing raw material are also varying. It is therefore difficult to quantitatively predict the properties of the final product. However, with development and much simpler access of supervised machine learning methods during the recent years, new powerful possibilities are available. The goal of the present thesis is to implement and evaluate some of these methods in order to predict the most important product properties for a real industrial board machine (thickness, bending stiffness, curl, twist) and their variability (for example expressed as standard deviation) based on data obtained from process data (for example fibre morphology, stock composition, stock treatment, stock concentration, jet/wire speed difference, fibre orientation profile). This model will then be used to identify the most sensitive process stage(s) in respect to product property variation.

Betreuer: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Samuel Schabel, TU Darmstadt
Tekn. Dr. Hannes Vomhoff, Holmen AB, Schweden

Darmstadt, den 28. September 2020

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Samuel Schabel

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Darmstadt, Wednesday 7th April, 2021

R. Othen

Abstract

This study shows that machine learning (ML) methods are applicable for predicting paperboard properties based on raw material and process data, e.g., bending stiffness and curl in machine direction (MD) and cross-machine direction (CD) so as the twist. The feature selection is crucial for the quality of the prediction. Therefore, domain knowledge is needed to select the right features. This selection improves the model and ensures its reliability, comprehensibility, and interpretability.

The following procedure was conducted in this study: preprocessing, feature selection, prediction, and variability analysis. The self-implemented recursive feature addition (RFA) takes the features specified by a domain expert during feature selection into consideration and requires less computation time in comparison to the common recursive feature elimination (RFE).

The extremely randomized tree (ET) was chosen due to its high interpretability and good results. It achieves a mean absolute error (MAE) for the bending stiffness MD of 0.79 mN m; an MAE for curl MD of 0.05 m^{-1} (in a value range from 7 to 100 mN m and -1 to 1 m^{-1} , respectively); and similar results for the respective CD properties.

A variability analysis was performed, identifying the features that bring variability to the examined property. For bending stiffness these are combinations of basis weight, thickness, and tambour speed; for curl, they are combinations of refining energy to the long-fiber, water into the liquid application system, and pressure in the drying cylinders.

Finally, for the prediction of twist with the same feature set as for curl MD, the R^2 score achieves 0.2755 and a MAE of 0.10 m^{-1} (in a value range of -1 to 1 m^{-1}). This demonstration clearly shows the importance of specifying the most relevant features for each property.

The respective code can be found at [1].

Keywords

prediction, paperboard, bending stiffness, curl, twist, machine learning, decision trees, extremely randomized trees

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

Symbol	Description	Symbol	Description
AI	artificial intelligence	nan	not a number
ANN	artificial neural network	No.	number of
CART	classification and regression trees	OLS	ordinary least squares
CD	cross-machine direction	ReLU	rectified linear unit
DT	decision tree	RF	random forest
ET	extremely randomized tree	RFA	recursive feature addition
KM	board machine	RFE	recursive feature elimination
Lasso	least absolute shrinkage and selection operator	RH	relative humidity
MAE	mean absolute error	RMSE	root mean squared error
max. abs. error	maximum absolute error	SHAP	Shapley additive explanation
MCA	multicollinearity analysis	SVR	support vector regression
MD	machine direction	VDE	Verband der Elektrotechnik
ML	machine learning	VDI	Verband deutscher Ingenieure
MLP	multi-layer perceptron	XAI	explainable AI
MSE	mean squared error		

Latin letters

Symbol	Description	Unit
S_b	bending stiffness	mN m
R^2	coefficient of determination	-
K_x	curl along x-axis (MD)	m^{-1}
K_y	curl along y-axis (CD)	m^{-1}
K_{xy}	diagonal curl (twist)	m^{-1}
F	force	N
G	gini impurity	-
\mathbb{L}	loss	-
\mathbf{W}	matrix containing $\mathbf{w}_{1,\dots,m}$ vectors of weights	-

Symbol	Description	Unit
X	matrix containing $x_{1,\dots,m}$ vectors of features	-
Y	matrix containing $y_{1,\dots,t}$ vectors of targets	-
m	number of features	-
n	number of samples	-
t	number of targets	-
J	objective function	-
l_s	sample length	m
b_s	sample width	m
b	value of one bias	-
x	value of one feature sample	-
\hat{y}	value of one prediction	-
y	value of one target sample	-
w	value of one weight	-
\mathbf{b}	vector containing $b_{1,\dots,n}$ bias	-
\mathbf{w}	vector containing $w_{1,\dots,n}$ weights	-
\mathbf{x}	vector containing $x_{1,\dots,n}$ samples of features	-
$\hat{\mathbf{y}}$	vector containing $y_{1,\dots,n}$ predictions	-
\mathbf{y}	vector containing $y_{1,\dots,n}$ samples of the target	-

Greek letters

Symbol	Description	Unit
α_b	bending angle	°
π	geometrical constant (3.14159)	-
α	parameter	-
ρ	parameter	-
ϵ	parameter	-
σ	standard deviation	-

1. Introduction and motivation

This study deals with methods to predict paperboard properties and their variability. It is written in cooperation with *Holmen Iggesund* in Iggesund, Sweden. *Holmen Iggesund* delivers 500 000 t/yr of paperboard of which 340 000 t/yr comes from *Iggesunds Bruk*. The following study is done with data from the past year of board machine (KM) 2, which produces 195 000 t/yr.

Holmen Iggesund's products are preferred by emerging brands and used for everything from champagne boxes and cosmetic packaging to pharmaceuticals and food. They deliver sustainably produced paperboard with outstanding properties and performance. To ensure this quality, it is important to conduct regular quality control checks. Unfortunately, some properties cannot be measured during production, but only after completion of a whole roll. These include the bending stiffness and the out-of-plane deformation when the product is exposed to moisture changes, i.e., curl and twist.

In the past, machine learning methods have evolved and become easier to implement [2, 3]. Machine learning is a versatile technology that is used in a wide variety of industry applications. In particular, the increase in usable data, more powerful computers, as well as techniques of deep learning has led to an increase in the popularity of these applications [4]. Some of these methods are investigated concerning their applicability for prediction. Since several properties of the board cannot be measured during production, but only after completion of a reel, at *Iggesunds Bruk* every ≈ 45 min.

Controlling product properties when the actual value can only be measured every ≈ 45 min is difficult and can be expensive, especially if the board is outside the specification. Then it has to be re-pulped and raw materials, as well as energy and time, were wasted.

Therefore, a prediction of the current value during production or even a forecast of future values is very helpful. Moreover, it allows the operator to recognize deviations at an early stage and to counteract them.

Bending stiffness is the most important mechanical property for packaging purposes. It is what gives boxes and panels their rigidity. The bending stiffness is developed throughout the paper forming process and is influenced by many parameters. Flatness and good dimensional stability when the product is exposed to moisture are critical paperboard properties. Curl and twist, in particular, are of great importance for good runability throughout the paperboard converting process, including packaging line efficiency. It is the most obvious paper property that can be easily checked and found by customers in their everyday printing jobs. It can be recognized by the fact that the colors from the multicolor print are not on top of each other, but offset, as a result of deformation.

The objective of this study is to find out how such models can be built, to predict the bending stiffness, curl, and twist of the paperboard with raw material and process data. In addition, the cause of variability in these properties should be found out.

2. The paperboard production (at *Iggesunds Bruk*)

The mill, in which this study was conducted is *Iggesunds Bruk* in Sweden. This chapter describes its paperboard production. *Iggesunds Bruk* has two board machines: board machine (KM) 1 and KM 2. This study was conducted on the KM 2 which produces 195 000 t/yr a fully bleached board composed of 3 layers for packaging and graphic purposes in a grammage range from 180 to 400 g/m² with a speed from 300 to 550 m/min. The machine is 270 m long. The produced board has a width of 4.65 m.

The following will briefly describes the board-making process and paperboard properties. Bending stiffness, curl, and twist, the properties that are considered in this study, are described in more detail. For further information please consider the literature [5, 6].

To give an overview, the general flow of the process is presented, followed by a more detailed description. The basic features of the KM 2 are shown in Figure 2.1. The objective of the process on the paper machine is to produce a continuous paper web of the required quality, uniform in the machine direction (MD), and cross-machine direction (CD) [5, 6]. The process consists of the approach flow system, the headbox, and the wire section, which in Figure 2.1 is referred to as formation/dewatering, the press section, and the dryer section. Online measurement of the moisture is implemented just before the surface sizing. Another drying section is installed before glazing (calendering) and coating. Further online measurements of the final properties of the paperboard (see Section 2.1) are conducted before winding (reeling).

Figure 2.1: The paperboard machine, consisting of different sections and online measurements [7].

After the production of one whole reel, sampling is done and offline measurements are conducted in the lab by the *L&W Autoline automated paper and board testing system* [8].

Approach flow system

The tasks of the approach flow system are to meter and dose the required components (different kinds of fibers, mineral, and chemical additives). Furthermore, it mixes the stock components to a uniform suspension and removes contaminants that were not removed in the stock preparation or were generated in the wet end process. Lastly, the suspension is diluted to headbox concentration. Once concluded, it provides a highly uniform flow to the headbox in terms of concentration, composition, and pressure, to name but a few. [5]

Iggesunds Bruk has the *PulpEye* [9] online measurement integrated into the pulp mill and stock preparation section, which measures fiber properties, such as freeness, kinks, brightness, length, and width.

Headbox

The purpose of the headbox is to distribute the suspension in the cross-machine direction of the paper machine and supply a suspension jet of high uniformity. The required high uniformity of the suspension jet relates to uniform fiber and filler dispersion, to equal velocity and thickness, as well as its orientation (exactly into machine direction and in one plain) over the whole machine width (cross-machine direction (CD)) and time. The fiber orientation in the jet will differ between the top and bottom sides of the jet, which may lead to quality problems such as curl and twist (see paragraph “Curl and twist” in Section 2.1). [5]

Wire section

In the wire section, the suspension supplied by the headbox is formed to a fiber web. The kind and quality of the suspension delivered from the headbox to the wire has a strong impact on the quality of the paper web formed. Therefore, the headbox and wire section – together with the approach flow system – must always be regarded as one interdependent unit. The main objectives of the wire section and their principal solutions are as follows: extensive separation of fibers, fillers, and fines from water, done by drainage perpendicular to the wire; and well-ordered and defined deposition of the fibers on the wire, obtained by oriented shear due to the velocity difference between the wire and suspension jet exiting the headbox, to name but a few. [5]

On *Iggesunds Bruk's* KM 2, three individual webs are formed in the wire section. These webs are combined at the end of the wire section to a 3-ply board. Furthermore, the fiber orientation of the surface of the two outer layers is measured. This is advantageous to model the bending stiffness as well as the curl and twist since the fiber orientation has a big influence on these properties (see Section 2.1).

Press section

The aim of the press section is to increase the dry content of the paper web by compression. This kind of mechanical dewatering reduces steam consumption in the dryer section and increases the strength of the web to avoid web breaks during the transfer of the paper web to the dryer section and the drying

process. Mechanical compression in the press section significantly affects the paper structure and surface properties. Sheet densification influences porosity, thickness, bulk, and internal bonding strength. [5]

Dryer section

The main purpose of the dryer section is to increase the dry content of the paper web by evaporation. Usually to a dryness between 90 to 98 %. During drying, the fibers develop hydrogen bonds that provide the natural strength of the paper web. The highest impact occurs at the end of the drying process, as can be derived from the free shrinkage. The direction of curl (MD, CD, or twist may occur) is determined by the paper and fiber structure. Curl can be reduced by adjusting the steam pressure of the top and bottom drying cylinders in a double-tier dryer group. [5]

Surface sizing and coating

Surface sizing is usually an online process in the paper machine, where a starch solution, and/or other sizing agents are applied to the paper web. The adhesive properties of the sizing solution, which is pressed into the fibrous network, lead to a considerably higher strength of sized papers than unsized papers. For increased tensile strength, penetration of the size into the paper is desired. If the main objective is to increase surface strength, for example, for printing, the size should remain on the surface. [5]

During coating, a water- and pigment-based dispersion is applied to the web to enhance its surface quality. Quality improvement can aim at optical properties such as whiteness, gloss, or opacity; tactile properties such as smoothness; and, most importantly, printability and print image quality. [5]

Iggesunds Bruk uses the blade coating technology to be able to coat both sides twice.

Calendering

The objective of calendering is to improve the surface characteristics of paper for its further use, for example, printing. Different technological properties are focused. These are mainly: gloss; smoothness/roughness; and density, to name but a few. Smoothing the surface and increasing gloss are accompanied by a reduction in thickness, strength properties, brightness, and opacity to a certain degree. [5]

Reeling

The purpose of reeling is to wind up the continuously produced paper web on tambours, building up paper rolls, so-called reels. [5]

Sampling

Sampling is done to measure paperboard properties offline. Since some properties, such as bending stiffness, curl and twist, can not be measured online, this is inevitable. After the production of a whole reel, at *Iggesunds Bruk* usually every ≈ 45 min, a sample strip in CD is taken (see Figure 2.2) from the

very end of the reel. It should be pointed out that the properties measured on the CD strip are the result of the process conditions at that particular point in time, and not the entire reel. As we know that there are process variations in MD, i.e., taking a sample at a slighter later time will therefore lead to different measurement results. Measurement is done automatically with the *L&W Autoline automated paper and board testing system* [8]. It measures different paperboard properties at various CD positions. The measured data is saved automatically to the database with the timestamp from the processing time, i.e., machine reel turn-up time and not the time when the measurement was made or when the value was entered into the database.

Figure 2.2: Quality control procedure [10].

Furthermore, all the online measurements (i.e., from the measurement frames in the machine, the *PulpEye*, and other sensors) are also saved to the database with the timestamp of the processing time. The measurement frequency is once a minute. At *Iggesunds Bruk* not every measured value is saved, only when the change in the value exceeds a certain threshold. In the past, these thresholds were set individually and specifically for each measurement. For other measured values, if this threshold is not exceeded, “nan” (not a number) is saved. This procedure is used to save data storage space.

2.1. Paperboard properties

Paper is a highly anisotropic material with three distinct orientations defined as machine direction (MD), cross-machine direction (CD), and thickness direction (ZD), see Figure 2.2. The properties of the thickness direction are not examined in this study.

In general, paper properties can be divided into seven major groups: basic, strength, stiffness, optical, surface, structural, and absorption properties. Basic properties are basis weight, thickness, density (ratio of basis weight and thickness), filler content, and moisture [11]. Among all properties, some specific ones characterize the paperboard and are required [5]:

- Strength/stiffness properties such as bending stiffness (bulk and Young's modulus) to protect the packed goods against damage.
- Flatness, plybond, creasability, and punching to ensure good runability in converting and packaging lines.
- Resistance against moisture, gas, and flavor to protect the goods from quality changes.
- Free from impurities such as microorganisms, toxic or mutagenous substrates, and taint or odor to protect the goods from contamination.
- Brightness, gloss, roughness, and printability of the surface to ensure appealing information, identification, and promotion of the packed goods.

This study deals with the bending stiffness and flatness (in the following referred to as curl and twist) of the paperboard. Therefore these are described in more detail in the following paragraphs. In this study, the focus lays on the bending stiffness and flatness, here referred to as curl and twist.

Bending stiffness

Resistance to bending is the force required to bend a rectangular paperboard sample by an angle of 15° . Bending stiffness is calculated from the force registered at an angular deflection of 5° . For the majority of paperboards, a bending angle of 15° greatly exceeds the elastic limit. An angle of 5° , however, usually remains within the elastic limit and is accepted as a standard value. Set-up accuracy is very important since a degree of error of only 0.5° will result in a measurement error of 10 %. Bending stiffness, bending resistance, and bending moment are measured using the two-point method as shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Measuring arrangement to test the bending stiffness [12].

In this method, one end of the sample is fastened in a clamp, and a force F is applied at a distance l_s from the clamp. The bending angle, α_b , is the angle by which the clamp is rotated during the test. The bending stiffness S_b is measured according to [12] by calculating:

$$S_b = \frac{60}{\pi} \frac{F_{\alpha_b} l_s^2}{\alpha_b b_s}, \quad (\text{Eq. 2.1})$$

where:

F_{α_b} bending force at α_b

α_b bending angle

l_s sample length

b_s sample width

Iggesunds Bruk measures the bending stiffness at $\alpha_b = 5^\circ$ and uses a sample size of $0.05 \text{ m} \times 0.038 \text{ m}$ ($l_s \times b_s$), simplifying Equation 2.1 to

$$S_b = 0.2514 \times F_{5^\circ}. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.2})$$

The bending stiffness is influenced by several parameters, the most important ones are: pulp fractions (in each layer), basic properties (in each layer), fiber properties (in each layer), fiber orientation (in each layer), drying shrinkage, and surface starch/coating [13, 14, 15]. This list leads to the process parameters: fiber type, refining conditions, consistency in flow to the headbox, amount of flow to the headbox, jet-to-wire ratio, line load in the press section, temperature/pressure in the drying section, speed differences (draw), coating type, coating amount, and line load in the calender.

Figure 2.4 shows the histograms of the measurement of bending stiffness from one-year data.

(a) Histogram of measurement of bending stiffness MD (b) Histogram of measurement of bending stiffness CD

Figure 2.4: Histogram of measurement of bending stiffness from one year data.

Curl and twist

Curl in the finished product manifests itself as rolling of the paper when it undergoes changes in moisture and temperature. The paper is deformed to a bowl or cylindrical shape. It is composed of three independent components K_x (curl MD), K_y (curl CD), and K_{xy} (twist) which result in the total curl, see Figure 2.5a. The cause is generally by z-directional inhomogeneities in swelling or shrinkage of the paper and an asymmetrical drying of the top and bottom sides of the web. This inhibits tensions that can be released again when humidity and temperature change. Diagonal curl (twist) is always related to fiber orientation. The most important cause is the two-sidedness of the fiber orientation angle. [6, 16] Curl is influenced by several parameters, the most important ones are: paper grade, percentage softwood, percentage broke (recycled scrapped paper), power used in the refiners to process the hardwood in two refiners, thickness, ash content, moisture content, porosity measure, and the difference in levels of surface moisture [17, 18]. For more details about bending stiffness, curl, and twist, please consider the literature [19, 20].

(a) Sheet curl consists of three independent components: K_x (curl MD), K_y (curl CD) and K_{xy} (twist) [20]

(b) The curl and twist tester from *Lorentzen & Wettre Company*. A) Traversing, noncontact distance-meter, B) Test piece holder rack, C) Micro-processor, D) Conditioning unit [21]

Figure 2.5: Description of curl and twist and its measurement device.

To measure the curl and twist of paperboard a tester from *Lorentzen & Wettre Company* (now *ABB* [22]) is used (Figure 2.5b). The measuring principle is based on an optical non-contact meter that scans the u -deflection of five test pieces each $100 \text{ mm} \times 100 \text{ mm}$ in size. Each test piece is mounted at its center on a flat circular pillar and fixed by a magnet giving a supporting area of approximately 25 mm^2 . This leaves the rest of the test piece free for out-of-plane movements. On each test piece, measurements of deflections (u) are made at 9×9 points, 10 mm apart, the fixed center excluded. Therefore, the maximum deflection which can be measured is $\pm 10 \text{ mm}$. During the evaluation, the humidity in the climate chamber is set to three levels and out-of-plane deformation is evaluated at three different

levels of relative humidity (RH): 35, 50, and 65 % at 23 °C. A complete test includes conditioning and measurement in all these conditioning atmospheres. At the end of each conditioning period, the deflections of each test piece are determined. [21] In this study, the conditioning at 50 % RH is considered.

Figures 2.6 and 2.7 show the histograms of measurement of curl and twist from one-year data.

(a) Histogram of measurement of curl MD

(b) Histogram of measurement of curl CD

Figure 2.6: Histogram of measurement of curl from one year data.

Figure 2.7: Histogram of measurement of twist from one year data.

3. Machine learning (ML)

Machine learning (ML) is a branch of artificial intelligence (AI), as shown in Figure 3.1. Algorithms in ML are programmed to be able to learn from data. In contrast to traditional programming, the product of the algorithm is not a direct numerical output, but a function, which is illustrated in Figure 3.2. This enables machine learning to tackle problems that cannot be solved by a human with traditional programming. [4]

Figure 3.1: The landscape of machine learning, based on [23].

Figure 3.2: Comparison of traditional programming and machine learning, based on [24].

In the context of ML, the term learning from data with n samples refers to approximating the function

$$\mathbf{Y} = f(\mathbf{X}), \quad (\text{Eq. 3.1})$$

where $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_m\}$ is the input matrix, each entry of $\mathbf{x}_i = \{x_{i,1}, x_{i,2}, \dots, x_{i,n}\}$ is referred to as one of m so-called features with n samples to the target matrix $\mathbf{Y} = \{\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_t\}$ and each entry of $\mathbf{y}_j = \{y_{j,1}, y_{j,2}, \dots, y_{j,n}\}$ is referred to as one of t so-called labels with n samples [25].

Learning the function $f(\mathbf{X})$ can be supervised or unsupervised. The difference between these two techniques lies in the data set used for the application. With unsupervised learning, features are extracted from the data set in the form of individual features [4]. In supervised learning, a dataset containing features is used. Additionally, a label is assigned to each of the feature \mathbf{x}_i . These labels represent the target vector \mathbf{y}_j in supervised learning [26].

In the following, only the functionality of supervised learning is presented and explained, since only this is relevant to this study. For further information on unsupervised learning, please refer to the literature [4, 25].

Within supervised learning, a distinction is made between classification and regression. In classification, a ML algorithm must assign one of the k classes to an input. Therefore, the learnable function $f(\mathbf{X})$ must have the following form: $f : \mathbb{R}^{n \times m} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, k\}^t$ [4].

In regression, a ML algorithm must determine a numerical value for the output from an input and thus $f(\mathbf{X})$ follows the form: $f : \mathbb{R}^{n \times m} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times t}$ [4].

Numerical values are to be predicted in this study, therefore, only regression is discussed. The mathematical description covers the general case considering m features and t targets. The number of t targets is limited to one since a separate model is created for each paperboard property to increase the understanding of the coherences. Thus, no multiple regression is performed to predict multiple targets at once, and the mathematical description is simplified to

$$f : \mathbb{R}^{n \times m} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n, \quad f(\mathbf{X}) = \mathbf{y}. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.2})$$

In this study, various prediction methods of ML are used. The different predictors that are examined in this study are described in Section 3.3. To perform such a prediction, suitable features (process signals) must first be selected from a large number of available features. This so-called feature selection is described in Section 3.2. One of the main aims of regression analysis is to isolate the relationship between each independent variable (features) and the dependent variable (target). Hence, correlating features can cause problems, with adjusting the model and interpreting the results. This problem is addressed with the help of multicollinearity analysis (MCA), which is described in Section 3.1.

Train-validation-test split

In the context of ML, it is common to split the dataset into three parts: training, validation, and test sets. There is no universal specification for the division of the dataset. In particular, the split depends on the amount of data. Proportions of the training set between 66 to 98 % of the dataset are common. A proportionally large training set is only legitimate if the validation and test set allows evaluation of the training despite small proportions. This is especially possible with very large datasets with more than one million samples. [4]

The optimization algorithm is applied to the training set to adjust the learnable parameters. The validation set is used to evaluate the learning progress of the model during the training. The quality of a trained model is evaluated using the data it has not worked with yet. The test set is designed for this purpose. [4] The process of having the train-validation-test split is illustrated in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Purpose of the train-validation-test split.

3.1. Multicollinearity analysis (MCA)

Multicollinearity occurs when independent variables are correlated in a regression model, causing an unwanted dependency. Fitting the regression model and interpreting the results can be complicated if the correlation degree exceeds a certain threshold. As a result, the difficulty is to independently estimate the relationship between each feature and the target increases, as the features tend to change together. [27] A multicollinearity analysis (MCA) between features can be performed to remove highly correlating features. For correlation analysis, for example, Pearson's or Spearman's correlation coefficient can be applied.

Pearson's correlation coefficient

Pearson's correlation coefficient $r_{\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j}$ evaluates the linear relationship between two features \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j . [27, 28] It is computed by dividing the covariance of \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j with the product of their standard deviations $\sigma_{\mathbf{x}_i}$ and $\sigma_{\mathbf{x}_j}$ as [27]

$$r_{\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j} = \frac{\text{COV}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)}{\sigma_{\mathbf{x}_i} \sigma_{\mathbf{x}_j}}. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.3})$$

Spearman's correlation coefficient

Spearman's correlation coefficient $r_{S_{i,j}}$ evaluates the monotonic relationship between two continuous or ordinal variables. In a monotonic relationship, the variables tend to change together, but not necessarily at a constant rate. [28]

Similar to Pearson's correlation coefficient, it is defined between the rank variables. [29] If $rg_{\mathbf{x}_i}$ and $rg_{\mathbf{x}_j}$ are calculated for each sample, the Spearman correlation coefficient with the covariance $\text{cov}(rg_{\mathbf{x}_i}, rg_{\mathbf{x}_j})$ and the standard deviations $\sigma_{rg_{\mathbf{x}_i}}, \sigma_{rg_{\mathbf{x}_j}}$ of the two rank variables are calculated as [30]

$$r_{S_{i,j}} = r_{rg_{\mathbf{x}_i}, rg_{\mathbf{x}_j}} = \frac{\text{COV}(rg_{\mathbf{x}_i}, rg_{\mathbf{x}_j})}{\sigma_{rg_{\mathbf{x}_i}} \sigma_{rg_{\mathbf{x}_j}}}. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.4})$$

Both Pearson's and Spearman's correlation coefficients range between $[-1, 1]$. The basic difference between the two correlation coefficients is that the Pearson correlation coefficient can only be applied with a linear relationship between the two variables, while the Spearman correlation coefficient also operates with monotonic relationships. [28] For that reason, Spearman's correlation coefficient will be used in the following study.

3.2. Feature Selection

When working with thousands of different features, some are bound to be relevant in describing the process while others have less influence on the process. Feature selection deals with the process of selecting the most relevant features among existing features. [28]

There are three main objectives in feature selection [31]:

1. Provide better insight into the underlying process.
2. Since ML algorithms fit their view of reality based on the data, they are trained on they tend to find patterns within the noise.
3. If a predictor is to be implemented, the limitation of the feature set makes models both smaller, faster, and more cost-efficient.

Following from this: If the number of (No.) investigated process variables can be reduced, it becomes easier for domain experts to analyze and validate produced models [31].

There are three main classes of methods for performing the feature selection, which will be described in the following [31]:

1. Filters
2. Wrappers
3. Embedded methods

Filters

Filter methods analyze the correlation between features and the target. They do not consider what model is to be implemented (which predictor is used) in the end, rather than relying completely on correlation. [31] Two filter methods examined in this study are the univariate linear regression test and mutual information.

The univariate linear regression test computes the F score pairwise. This is done in two steps: The correlation between each feature x_i and the target y is computed with Pearson's correlation coefficient $r_{x_i,y}$ before it is converted to an F score. [32]

Mutual information between two random variables is represented by a non-negative value, which measures the dependency between the variables. It is equal to zero if, and only if, two random variables are independent, which means that higher values mean higher dependency. The function relies on nonparametric methods based on entropy estimation from k-nearest neighbors distances as described in [33] and [34]. [32] Similar to the univariate linear regression test, the mutual information is computed for each feature x_i and target y .

To achieve an actual feature selection, all but the k highest scoring features are removed, where k is a user-defined number.

Wrappers

Wrappers iteratively create subsets of features that are used to form models. These models are trained and validated on a hold-out validation set, to measure the error rate of given different feature subsets. The advantage of wrappers is that they can be tuned and evaluated on specific modeling algorithms, resulting in the best feature set. Unfortunately, wrappers are computationally expensive, since there are many feature sets to train and evaluate combinatorially. The combinatorial possibilities in feature sets often make a wrapper infeasible to use on large-scale problems. If the feature set is large, a search strategy is needed, such as best-first, branch-and-bound, simulated annealing, or genetic algorithms. [31]

Even though none of the the wrapper methods are examined in this study, as they are computationally expensive, they are mentioned.

Embedded methods

To not have as high of computationally costs as with wrappers, but not only rely on correlations as with filters, embedded methods have been developed. To do so, embedded methods incorporate a predictor (the ones used in this study are described in Section 3.3) in its feature selection. [31] Two embedded methods examined in this study are recursive feature elimination (RFE) and recursive feature addition (RFA). It is mentioned that the RFE is an implemented algorithm in [32], whereas the RFA is an algorithm written by the author. Both algorithms train a certain predictor, defined by the user, that assigns weights to features (e.g., the coefficients of a linear model). The two approaches are described below.

Recursive feature elimination (RFE)

RFE aims to select features by recursively considering smaller and smaller sets of features. First, the predictor is trained on the entire feature set. The importance of each feature is obtained through the weighting. Then, the least important feature is pruned from the current set of features. That procedure is recursively repeated on the pruned set until the desired number of features is eventually selected [32, 35]. Another approach is storing the feature's performance by a score function (e.g., R^2 score (see Section 3.4)) while pruning until there are no more features in the pruned set. Lastly, the performance profile is plotted and the smallest feature set with the best performance is chosen [31]. The latter approach is used in this study.

Recursive feature addition (RFA)

The RFA aims to select features by recursively considering greater and greater sets of features. First, the predictor is trained on a set of predefined features. This initial feature set is designed by domain experts and an intensive literature review, which includes features that physically affect the target. The predictor is trained and an R^2 score (see Section 3.4) is calculated. Next, another feature is added from a sorted list. This sorted list contains the remaining features ranked by a univariate linear regression test. Each of the remaining features is added temporary one at a time. A R^2 score is calculated with the temporary set and stored. The feature which brings the greatest gain in the R^2 score is added permanently. To save computation time, only the top twenty features from the sorted list are considered when adding features, as well as restricting the total number of features to add. Lastly, the performance profile is plotted and the smallest feature set with the best performance is chosen.

The RFA method is a self-implemented approach, which is not provided by the *sklearn* (*sci-kit learn*) package [32].

3.3. Predictors

Predictors take a dataset of instances and return a dataset of predictions. This section describes the predictors used in this study. These are namely:

1. Ridge
2. Least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (Lasso)
3. Elastic Net
4. Linear support vector regression (SVR)
5. Decision tree (DT)
6. Random forest (RF)
7. Extremely randomized tree (ET)
8. Multi-layer perceptron (MLP)

The first three of the above methods are based on an ordinary least squares (OLS) linear regression in which the objective function J is defined as [28, 32]

$$J_{\text{OLS}}(\mathbf{w}) = \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\mathbf{w}\|_2^2, \quad \text{where } \hat{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{w} \quad (\text{Eq. 3.5})$$

denotes the vector of the predicted values $\{\hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \dots, \hat{y}_n\}$ and $\|\mathbf{u}\|_2 := \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n u_i^2}$ the ℓ_2 -norm of a vector $\mathbf{u} = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$, is minimized by adjusting the weights $\mathbf{w} = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$ for n samples.

Ridge

Each of the following three methods adds a regularization term to the objective function. In particular, the objective function with a user-definable parameter $\alpha \geq 0$ for the Ridge regression the ℓ_2 -norm of the vector \mathbf{w} is added [28, 32, 36]

$$J_{\text{Ridge}}(\mathbf{w}) = \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\mathbf{w}\|_2^2 + \alpha \|\mathbf{w}\|_2^2. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.6})$$

Least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (Lasso)

In the objective function with a user-definable parameter $\alpha \geq 0$ for the least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (Lasso) regression is [28, 32, 37, 38]

$$J_{\text{Lasso}}(\mathbf{w}) = \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\mathbf{w}\|_2^2 + \alpha \|\mathbf{w}\|_1, \quad (\text{Eq. 3.7})$$

in which the ℓ_1 -norm, denoted by $\|\mathbf{u}\|_1 := \sum_{i=1}^n |u_i|$, is added.

Elastic Net

The objective function for the Elastic Net method combines the ℓ_1 and the ℓ_2 -norm, the ratio of which is set with user-definable parameters $\alpha \geq 0$ and $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$ [28, 32, 37, 38]

$$J_{\text{Elastic Net}}(\mathbf{w}) = \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\mathbf{w}\|_2^2 + \alpha\rho\|\mathbf{w}\|_1 + \frac{\alpha(1-\rho)}{2}\|\mathbf{w}\|_2^2. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.8})$$

Linear support vector regression (SVR)

In simple regressions, the error is minimized. While in linear support vector regression (SVR) the error is fit within a certain threshold ϵ . The objective function to minimize for the linear SVR method is [28, 39]

$$J_{\text{SVR}}(\mathbf{w}) = \frac{1}{2}\|\mathbf{w}\|_2^2, \quad \text{with subject to } \mathbf{y} \pm \mathbf{X}\mathbf{w} \leq \epsilon. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.9})$$

These predictors are provided by the package *sklearn* (*sci-kit learn*) [32] and standard setup for the parameters is $\alpha = 1, \rho = 0.5, \epsilon = 0.0$ [32].

Decision tree (DT)

A decision tree (DT) as the name suggests works on a set of decisions derived from the data and its behavior. It does not use a linear regressor, so its performance is independent of the linear nature of the data. One of the other most important reasons to use tree models is that they are very easy to interpret. The decision trees use the classification and regression trees (CART) algorithm. They are powerful algorithms, capable of fitting complex datasets. Additionally, they require very little to no data preparation, as is the case with scaling. [28]

Since they are so easy to interpret and visualize, the following describes the basics using the iris flower dataset, introduced by Fisher [40] and very popular in the *sklearn* (*sci-kit learn*) [32] package. While it is a classification problem for flowers, the same principles apply to the regression problem considered in this study. A DT trained on the dataset is shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Iris decision tree [28].

Assuming an iris flower with a petal length of 1.4 cm and width of 0.2 cm is to be classified, in the first step in the root node, the value of the length is compared with 2.45 cm. Since it is smaller (true), the root's left child node (depth 1, left) is selected and the class setosa is predicted. In this case, it is a leaf node (i.e., it does not have any child nodes). Now another flower with a petal length of 6 cm and a width of 2.5 cm is to be classified. Since the length is greater than 2.45 cm and the width is greater than 1.75 cm, the root's right child node is selected in each node (depth 2, right). The predicted class is now virginica. A node's sample attribute counts how many samples it applies to. [28]

Finally, the bottom line of this particular DT is that the gini value indicates the gini impurity: the gini value indicates the gini impurity: a node is pure (gini = 0) if all samples it applies to belong to the same class. The gini impurity G is computed by [28]

$$G_i = 1 - \sum_{k=1}^n p_{i,k}^2, \quad (\text{Eq. 3.10})$$

where $p_{i,k}^2$ is the ratio of class k samples among the training samples in the i^{th} node. The classification and regression trees (CART) algorithm splits the data set and generates nodes so that the gini impurity for each leaf node becomes minimal. [28]

Similar to the classification problem, a DT for a regression problem also uses a measure of impurity, namely the mean squared error (MSE) (see Section 3.4). Having a data set of a simple quadratic equation plus some noise, Figure 3.5a shows the graphical output of the trained DT with a restriction to the maximal depth to 2 ($\text{max_depth} = 2$), whereas Figure 3.5b shows the graphical output without restrictions. So by restricting the maximal depth of a decision tree, it can be seen as a piecewise constant approximation [32], otherwise the model is too sensitive and follows the noise in the data. It is one of the key issues in ML to find the right balance in terms of sensitivity.

(a) Prediction of a restricted decision tree model

(b) Prediction of an unrestricted decision tree model

Figure 3.5: Prediction of two decision tree models [28].

Sci-kit learn uses the classification and regression trees (CART) algorithm to train the DT. The algorithm works by splitting the training set into two subsets using a single feature and a threshold (e.g., “petal length ≤ 2.45 cm”). It searches for the pair that produces the purest subsets (weighted by their size). The objective function for a regression problem to minimize is [28, 32, 41, 42]

$$J_{\text{CART}} = \frac{n_{\text{left}}}{n} \text{MSE}_{\text{left}} + \frac{n_{\text{right}}}{n} \text{MSE}_{\text{right}} \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{cases} \text{MSE}_{\text{node}} = \sum_{i \in \text{node}} (y_i - \hat{y}_{\text{node}})^2, \\ \hat{y}_{\text{node}} = \frac{1}{n_{\text{node}}} \sum_{i \in \text{node}} y_i. \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. 3.11})$$

The the number of samples in the left/right subset is denoted by $n_{\text{left/right}}$.

Random forest (RF)

A group of DTs, each trained on a different random subset of the training set, is an example of an Ensemble method. To make final predictions, the predictions of all the individual trees are obtained, then they predict the class/value that will get the most votes. Such an ensemble of DTs is called a random forest (RF), which are among the most powerful ML algorithms available today. The trees in the RF are generally trained via the bagging method. Bagging (short for bootstrap aggregation) is used when the aim is to reduce the variance of a DT. In this instance, the idea is to create several subsets of data from the training sample chosen randomly with replacement. Now, each collection of subset data is used to train their decision trees. The result is an ensemble of different models which allow a more robust prediction than a single decision tree could have obtained by averaging the results of the different DTs. The RF algorithm introduces extra randomness when growing trees; instead of searching for the very best feature when splitting a node, it searches for the best feature among a random subset of features. The algorithm results in a greater tree diversity, which trades a higher bias for a lower variance, generally yielding an overall better model. [28, 43]

Extremely randomized tree (ET)

When growing a tree in an RF, at each node only a random subset of the features is considered for splitting. It is possible to make trees even more random by also using a random threshold for each feature rather than searching for the best possible thresholds. A forest of such extremely random trees is called an extremely randomized tree (ET) ensemble. Once again, this technique trades more bias for lower variance. It also makes ET much faster to train than regular RF, since finding the best possible threshold for each feature at every node is one of the most time-consuming tasks of growing a tree. [28, 44]

Multi-layer perceptron (MLP)

A multi-layer perceptron (MLP) is a class of feedforward artificial neural networks (ANNs). An MLP consists of at least three layers of nodes: an input, a hidden, and an output layer. Except for the input nodes, each node is a neuron that uses an activation function, which can be linear or nonlinear. MLP utilizes a supervised learning technique called backpropagation for training. [45]

The process of an MLP is divided into four steps [4]:

1. Forward pass
2. Compute loss
3. Backward pass
4. Adjusting weights

An example of an MLP is given in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Network graph for a $(L + 1)$ -layer perceptron network, based on [46].

Forward pass

In the forward pass, the MLP is run through once. The neurons of one layer receive the activation of the previous layer as input and after a mathematical operation they pass it on to the next layer [4]. A neuron with its inputs and outputs is shown in Figure 3.7 as an example.

Figure 3.7: Single processing unit and its components, based on [47].

The input of a neuron consists of the activations of the neurons of the previous layer, each of which is weighted. This weighting is reflected mathematically in the learnable parameters of the weight matrix \mathbf{W} . The sum of weighted inputs and a learnable bias b is subsequently given into an activation function.

This mathematical operation within the MLP is explained with the help of Equation 3.12 [4]:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = f_a(\mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{b}) = f_a(\mathbf{z}), \quad (\text{Eq. 3.12})$$

where:

- f_a activation function
- $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ predictions
- \mathbf{z} input of the activation function f_a
- \mathbf{X} matrix of the input
- \mathbf{W} matrix of weights
- \mathbf{b} bias

The described mathematical operation is implemented for a layer with index i in vectorized form. [4] Matrix multiplication is shown for a layer receiving l activations from the previous layer in Equation 3.13 for the output $\mathbf{z}^{[i]}$ in layer i [4]:

$$\mathbf{z}^{[i]} = \begin{matrix} & \mathbf{W}^{[i]} & & \mathbf{X}^{[i]} & & \mathbf{b}^{[i]} \\ & \begin{bmatrix} \dots & \mathbf{w}_1^{[i]} & \dots \\ \dots & \mathbf{w}_2^{[i]} & \dots \\ & \vdots & \\ \dots & \mathbf{w}_k^{[i]} & \dots \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}^{[i](1)} & \mathbf{x}^{[i](2)} & \dots & \mathbf{x}^{[i](l)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \end{bmatrix} & + & \begin{bmatrix} \dots & b_1^{[i]} & \dots \\ \dots & b_2^{[i]} & \dots \\ & \vdots & \\ \dots & b_k^{[i]} & \dots \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix} \cdot \quad (\text{Eq. 3.13})$$

Activation functions are used for mapping inputs to outputs with non-linear functions. Typically, an activation function $f_a(\mathbf{z})$ is applied element-wise to the output of the matrix multiplication in Equation 3.13 [4]. In modern MLPs, the use of rectified linear unit (ReLU) are used as a standard, determined by the activation function $f_a(\mathbf{z}) = \max\{0, \mathbf{z}\}$. Nevertheless, the choice of the activation function may differ within a network in different layers, and in the output layer depending on the use case. [4] For a more detailed discussion of the advantages and disadvantages of individual activation functions, please refer to the literature [4].

Compute loss

The loss \mathbb{L} is a measure of the deviation between the target \mathbf{y} and the result of the forward pass $\hat{\mathbf{y}} : \mathbb{L} = f_{\mathbb{L}}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}})$. In this case, the loss depends on the chosen loss function $f_{\mathbb{L}}$ [4]. Some typical loss functions are described in Section 3.4. For more details on loss functions, please refer to the literature [4, 25].

Backward pass

MLPs are based on minimizing an objective function J_{MLP} . In this context, the objective function to be minimized, is the loss function $f_{\mathbb{L}}$. Since the input of the function is usually a multidimensional vector,

there are many local minima in addition to one or more absolute minima. This fact complicates the optimization problem considerably. To minimize the objective function it is necessary to determine in which direction it decreases most rapidly. To do this, the gradients of the function are derived. [4] The function f is decreased by moving along the negative gradient. This method is known as gradient descent and proposes the following change for a new point x' [4]:

$$x' = x - \alpha \nabla f(x), \quad (\text{Eq. 3.14})$$

where α denotes the learning rate.

The determination of the gradients in the backward pass is done by the backpropagation algorithm, where the chain rule is used to determine an analytical solution of the gradients. In this process, the same step is repeated at each layer propagating backward to the first layer [4]. This step is illustrated in Figure 3.8. Here, the gradient of a learnable parameter w_i is calculated as a function of the loss $f_{\mathbb{L}}$ and the output of a layer \hat{y} :

$$\frac{\partial f_{\mathbb{L}}}{\partial w_i} = \frac{\partial f_{\mathbb{L}}}{\partial \hat{y}} \frac{\partial \hat{y}}{\partial w_i}. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.15})$$

Figure 3.8: Backward pass of gradients through the network, based on [46].

Adjusting weights

With the help of gradient descent, an optimization problem in the context of MLP can be tackled. For this purpose, all learnable parameters of the network are adjusted using Equation 3.14. In this equation, the learning rate α describes the step size in the gradient descent [4]. For the learnable parameters w and b , the update rules are thus:

$$w_{\text{new}} = w_{\text{old}} - \alpha \frac{\partial f_{\mathbb{L}}}{\partial w_{\text{old}}}, \quad b_{\text{new}} = b_{\text{old}} - \alpha \frac{\partial f_{\mathbb{L}}}{\partial b_{\text{old}}}. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.16})$$

The learning rate α represents a crucial parameter in ML. Learning rates can be chosen by using plots that show the loss function over time. A learning rate that is too small can lead to very slow learning, as well as learning that remains at a high loss level. The latter leads to loss remaining at a local minimum. On the other hand, if the learning rate is too high, there may be either large oscillations or a significant increase in the loss. [4]

The importance of the learning rate α in an optimization problem is illustrated in Figure 3.9 for three cases: Good ($\alpha = \alpha_{opt}$), too low ($\alpha < \alpha_{opt}$), and too high ($\alpha > \alpha_{opt}$) learning rates.

Figure 3.9: Effect of too high or too small learning rate α on loss, based on [48].

Model interpretability

Using a particular predictor, of the various predictors presented in this section, has advantages and disadvantages. Since the further course of this study is mainly about understanding the models, the interpretability is of high importance. In this case, the statement “models that are more complex are more accurate” [49] applies. This accuracy is thus in contrast to interpretability since complex models are more difficult to interpret, as Figure 3.10 shows. Decision trees are very straightforward to interpret, while deep neural networks are hard to interpret [50].

Figure 3.10: Trade-off between model interpretability and performance, and a representation of the area of improvement where the potential of XAI techniques and tools resides [49].

With the help of explainable AI (XAI), even more, complex models can be interpreted, see paragraph “Feature importance analysis using Shapley additive explanation (SHAP) values” in Section 3.4.

3.4. Evaluation metric

This section describes the metrics used in this study to evaluate the prediction. The following metrics are used and described below in this order:

- Mean squared error (MSE)
- Root mean squared error (RMSE)
- Mean absolute error (MAE)
- Maximum absolute error (max. abs. error)
- R^2 score
- Durbin–Watson test
- Feature importance analysis using Shapley additive explanation (SHAP) values
- Variability analysis

Mean squared error (MSE)

The mean squared error (MSE) is a risk metric corresponding to the expected value of the squared (quadratic) error or loss. In descriptive statistics, it is known as the variance. If \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of the i -th sample, and y_i is the corresponding true value, then the MSE estimated over n samples is defined as [32]

$$\text{MSE}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.17})$$

Root mean squared error (RMSE)

The root mean squared error (RMSE) is simply the root of the MSE described above. In descriptive statistics, it is known as standard deviation. It is defined as [32]

$$\text{RMSE}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = \sqrt{\text{MSE}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}})} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.18})$$

Mean absolute error (MAE)

The mean absolute error (MAE) computes the absolute error for each pair of true value y_i and predicted value \hat{y}_i divided by n samples which is defined as [32]

$$\text{MAE}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.19})$$

Maximum absolute error (max. abs. error)

The maximum absolute error (max. abs. error) computes the maximum residual error, a metric that captures the worst-case error between the predicted value \hat{y} and the true value y . It is defined as [32]

$$\text{max. abs. error}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = \max(|y_i - \hat{y}_i|). \quad (\text{Eq. 3.20})$$

R^2 score

The R^2 score (coefficient of determination) represents the proportion of variance (of \mathbf{y}) that has been explained by the independent variables in the model. It provides an indication for quality and therefore a measure of how well unseen samples are likely to be predicted by the model, through the proportion of explained variance. The R^2 score ranges from $[-1, 1]$. In *sci-kit learn*'s implementation of the R^2 score there is no lower bound. Therefore, in this study, the computed R^2 score is set to zero, if it is negative. If \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of the i -th sample and y_i is the corresponding true value for total n samples, the estimated R^2 score is defined as [32]

$$R^2 \text{ score}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}, \quad \text{where } \bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.21})$$

Durbin–Watson test

Autocorrelation appears often when working with time-series data. Autocorrelation refers to the degree of correlation of the same variable between two successive time intervals. It measures how the lagged version of the value of a variable is related to the original version in a time series. The consequences of having an autocorrelated error term are [51]:

1. The estimated slope coefficients are unbiased and consistent.
2. With positive autocorrelation the standard errors are biased and too small.
3. With negative autocorrelation the standard errors are biased and too large.

The Durbin–Watson statistic is a test statistic used to detect the presence of autocorrelation at lag 1 (first-order autocorrelation) in the residuals (prediction errors) from a regression analysis. With n as the number of samples and the residuals e , the test statistic is defined as [52]

$$d = \frac{\sum_{i=2}^n (e_i - e_{i-1})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2}, \quad \text{where } e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i, \quad (\text{Eq. 3.22})$$

and $d \in [0, 4]$. The further d is below or above 2, the greater the autocorrelation. If it is significantly smaller than 2, this indicates a positive autocorrelation. If it is significantly greater than 2, this indicates a negative autocorrelation. All values $1.5 < d < 2.5$, therefore, do not yet indicate a dangerous degree of autocorrelation. However, values $d < 1 \wedge d > 3$ are considered as an indication of a strong first-order autocorrelation. [53]

Feature importance analysis using Shapley additive explanation (SHAP) values

The feature importance analysis's purpose is to determine which features are the most important ones to the model output. To understand why a model makes a certain prediction various methods have recently been proposed to help interpret the predictions of complex models, but it is often unclear how these methods are related and when one method is preferable over another. To address this problem, Lundberg et al. [54] presents a unified framework for interpreting predictions using Shapley additive explanation (SHAP). SHAP assigns a value for a particular prediction to each feature. The SHAP values are the average of the marginal contributions across all permutations.

This method requires retraining the model on all feature subsets $S \subseteq F$, where F is the set of all features. It assigns a value to each feature that represents the effect on the model prediction of including that feature. To compute this effect, a model $f_{S \cup \{i\}}$ is trained with that feature present, and another model f_S is trained with the feature withheld. Then, predictions from the two models are compared on the current input $f_{S \cup \{i\}}(x_{S \cup \{i\}}) - f_S(x_S)$, where x_S represents the values of the input features in the set S . Since the effect of withholding a feature depends on other features in the model, the preceding differences are computed for all possible subsets $S \subseteq F \setminus \{i\}$. The SHAP values are then computed and used as feature attributions. They are a weighted average of all possible differences [54]

$$\phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq F \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|!(|F| - |S| - 1)!}{|F|!} [f_{S \cup \{i\}}(x_{S \cup \{i\}}) - f_S(x_S)]. \quad (\text{Eq. 3.23})$$

It is important to point out the SHAP values do not provide causality [54], so it is up to the domain expert to decide if they are meaningful or not.

According to Lätti [55], there are only 2 to 5 very important features capable to cause big changes fast. Therefore, the five most important features found by calculating the SHAP values are considered as the top five features, which are used in the further procedure of the variability analysis.

Variability analysis

The variability analysis is a self-developed procedure to identify those features which bring variation in the prediction (and so into the papermaking process). The idea behind this is the following: When the input values are not varying, neither is the prediction. Accordingly, it can be derived which feature(s) cause(s) the variability.

Therefore, the top five features are identified with the feature importance analysis. Next, a period is selected where the quality should be constant but the actual values vary around this set point. Then, every feature is set to its mean value for that period. A prediction is made, with a constant time series as a result. In the first step, each one of the top five features is set to its original value one by one. All five predictions are plotted together with the original prediction. The number of features out of the top five features which are set back to their original values is increased gradually up to five. For a number greater than one, different combinations of features are considered. Lastly, a visual inspection of the plots is done to identify the feature/combination of features that bring the variability into the process.

3.5. Limits of machine learning

In the last decade, the amount of industrial data has increased significantly, computing power has improved tremendously, and major theoretical advances in ML have been made [2]. Nevertheless, there are difficulties and limitations where even ML fails.

One of the difficulties is that not enough, or not enough usable data is available. In robotics, industrial production, medical and safety applications, some events occur only rarely, which is why they are underrepresented in the data. There may also be restrictions for reasons of data protection or copyright laws. In some cases, data exists but labels do not. In this case, unsupervised learning could help, by automatically generating missing labels. For autonomous agents, vehicles, and robots that require feedback on their actions, there is a growing interest in learning in simulations, as enough training data of all kinds can be generated. Performant learning with little training data is a field of research that is still wide open and expected to have a great influence on future developments. Ideally, the aim is to enable machines to learn based on a few examples or a combination of known examples. Implementing this capability in ML applications is referred to as “one-shot” or even “zero-shot” learning. [50]

The interpretability of ML applications is the most important research goal from the point of view of the experts consulted. The term explainable AI (XAI) has become established for this topic. A distinction is made between transparency and explainability. Transparency means that the behavior of the application is fully comprehensible. In practice, however, this requirement is difficult to fulfill, since many models are necessarily very complex. Explainability, on the other hand, means that the main influencing factors can be shown for a concrete individual decision by the application, which is sufficient in terms of the EU General Data Protection Regulation. Technically, it is also much easier to fulfill than transparency. A scientific challenge is to abstract the input data into concepts that make sense to humans. Other prototypical approaches provide representative individual cases to explain decisions. A desirable and important property is the interpretability of the models in general and their results in individual cases. A decision tree can be interpreted particularly well, an artificial neural network (ANN) poorly. The good scalability with increasing data volumes and the poor interpretability are reasons why the experts interviewed in the project consider deep learning to be necessary but not sufficient for successful ML applications. The choice of method should always be based on the requirements of the task. In Germany, many application areas for classical learning methods that require fewer data will persist and emerge – such as the support vector machines and kernel methods which are strongly represented there. However, the experts see even greater potential in combining machine learning methods with other forms of knowledge. [50]

In many application areas, experts use their formalizations to describe typical properties or the behavior of the systems under investigation. Such additional knowledge is not always complete and can be improved data-driven. In engineering, the physical behavior of machines and systems is usually expressed by extensive systems of differential equations, which are then used as so-called “white-box” models for simulation. In contrast, engineers refer to ANN and other data-driven ML models that learn a

function from input to output vectors from sample data as “black-box” models. Both have their respective advantages and disadvantages in terms of creation effort, accuracy and traceability, so a hybrid “grey-box” approach promises enormous advantages. [50]

Last, the amount of data itself is a limitation. Unlike a formula, which often has no limitation in its range of validity, with ML only interpolation can be done, but not extrapolation. ML has its view of reality concerning the data. If data is only available from a limited range of values, it becomes difficult to predict data for other ranges with ML. [56]

4. Review of the literature

This chapter gives a brief overview of what has been elaborated in science to date. The literature search is carried out by an intensive search in relevant scientific journals with the keywords: prediction, modeling, simulation, stiffness, curl, pulp, paper, board, production, process, and combinations of these. In a second step, the literature referenced in the appropriate studies is examined. This chapter does not claim to be complete, only a short overview is given to get an impression of the status quo and to show how far science has come in the field of modeling and finally predicting the paperboard process and properties, in particular bending stiffness, curl, and twist.

It was shown recently by Leiviskä in *Simulation in pulp and paper industry* in 1996 [57] what simulations are used for, what benefits they have and how they can be structured in general. This is based on physical models, which means that the relationships between input and output must be known to the modeler. This approach was also pursued industrially, for example in Gutman et al. in *Modelling and prediction of bending stiffness for paper board manufacturing* in 1998 [15]. Their predictor ran for several months and achieved an accuracy of 75 % within \pm one standard deviation.

The first to employ neural networks to predict paper curl, rather than simulate the actual physical relationships, was Edwards et al. in *Paper curl prediction - neural networks applied to the papermaking industry* in 1999 [17]. He trained neural networks on data from *Tullis Russell* to classify the current paper curl according to in- or out-specification with an error rate of 18.92 % as a result compared to a linear classifier with an error rate of 24.32 %. He concludes that the use of a non-linear neural network is thus beneficial for this task [17].

Further studies, on the topics of process modeling and prediction of paper properties, in particular curl, were conducted, among others, by Skoglund et al.; Bortolin; Nieminen et al.; and Erkkilä et al. in 2000–2017 [58, 59, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67]. They all deal with physical to semi-physical models of the process/paper properties. This tremendous amount of studies shows how much focus was given to models where the physics are clear and well understood. Nevertheless, in his study *On Modelling and Estimation of Curl and Twist in Multi-ply Paperboard* from 2002 Bortolin stated that in conclusion, the artificial neural network (ANN) from Edwards et al. in *Paper curl prediction - neural networks applied to the papermaking industry* in 1999 [17] seems to be slightly better than the grey-box predictor he developed, which is based on classical laminate theory [59]. In a second study, *On modelling of curl in multi-ply paperboard* in 2006, he added an outlier-detection and some more inputs to the model. The resulting model achieves an MSE of 0.12 m^{-2} for curl CD curl, 0.018 m^{-2} for curl MD, and 0.10 m^{-2} for the twist. “This accuracy in predicting online paperboard curl has not been achieved previously.” [66].

The amount of data generated has increased significantly and the computational power has improved over the last decade [2]. Also, the number of publications from the field of ML in the process industry has risen noticeably since 2013 [3]. As a standard for the implementation and operation of Big Data applications, the German Verband deutscher Ingenieure (VDI) and the Verband der Elektrotechnik (VDE), in short VDI/VDE, published in 2019–2020 the first three sheets of the guideline VDI/VDE 3714 *Implementierung und Betrieb von Big-Data-Anwendungen in der produzierenden Industrie* (Implementation and Operation of Big Data Applications) [68, 69, 70], another four sheets will follow.

In *Neural Prediction of Product Quality Based on Pilot Paper Machine Process Measurements* published in 2011 Nieminen et al. used a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) model to predict the laboratory measurements of paper quality using the instantaneous state of the papermaking production process. Actual industrial data from a pilot paper machine was used. The final model met its goal accuracy 95.7 % of the time at its best (tensile index quality) and 66.7 % at its worst (beta formation).

Recently Vandenbossche took a physical modeling approach at *Iggesunds Bruk* in *Prediction of paperboard thickness and bending stiffness based on process data* from 2019. Based on laminate theory, his model predicts the thickness and bending stiffness of the paperboard. The average thickness predictions are all underestimations within a 5 % error while the bending stiffness estimations vary a lot more from product to product; from 9 % underestimation to 32 % overestimation.

The presented studies dealt mainly with physical models in which all equations have to be known. A few attempts to solve these problems with machine learning (ML) approaches have already been addressed, mainly with MLPs. The knowledge gap is whether other methods from the field of ML are also suitable and how to set up these models will be the focus in the further course of this study. The exact aims will be presented in the next chapter.

5. Aims

This study aims to investigate the applicability and accuracy of different machine learning (ML) methods for predicting paperboard properties based on raw material and process data. The goal is not to find an ML method that can predict all properties simultaneously, but rather the most suitable method for a single property. The examined properties are bending stiffness, curl and twist. Furthermore, the focus is not on the most accurate prediction model, but on the best model to interpret. To develop such a model, meaningful features must be selected, from the large database, in advance. Again, ML methods to support this, are investigated. These are: Filters, the recursive feature elimination (RFE), and the recursive feature addition (RFA) with various predictors. The predictors are: Ridge, Least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (Lasso), Elastic Net, Linear support vector regression (SVR), Decision tree (DT), Random forest (RF), Extremely randomized tree (ET), and Multi-layer perceptron (MLP). Once such models are built, they shall be used to find out which features (process parameters) cause variability in the paperboard properties. To do this, on the one hand, a feature importance analysis using Shapley additive explanation (SHAP) values is performed to identify the most influential features, and on the other hand, a variability analysis is performed to finally identify the features that cause the variability in the property.

Ultimately, the average values of a CD measurement are always chosen to predict bending stiffness/curl. A method is developed that predicts the respective bending stiffness/curl at this location by simply replacing the mean values by the CD measurement position. The best model is used with the feature set from the curl MD to predict the twist since they have similar sources of influence. This is done to see how well it performs, as a kind of validation. Finally it also shows what problems occur and thus what changes would be necessary.

The main focus should always be on physical relationships and comprehensibility in all stages.

5.1. Assumptions and Simplification

In this study, some simplifications have been made. First, time delays in the process are not taken into account because they are small when compared to the sampling rate of the data used. Furthermore, no outliers are filtered out to be able to focus on the aims mentioned above. This approach allows creating models quickly, albeit with imperfect results. Further work can be done with these models, and opportunities for improvement becomes visible.

6. Experimental setup

This chapter describes the dataset and methods used in this study as well as the procedure to achieve the aims stated in Chapter 5, whereas the results are presented in Chapter 7.

Everything is implemented with *Python*, mainly with the packages *pandas* [71] (for data tables and manipulation) and *sklearn* (*sci-kit learn*) [32] (includes a variety of different machine learning methods). The respective code can be found at [1].

The overall procedure is illustrated in Figure 6.1: First, the data is gathered. Next, it is preprocessed while loading it and performing a multicollinearity analysis (MCA). These steps are described in Section 6.1. Next, the feature selection is performed for each one to predict paper properties. The different approaches of feature selection are described in Section 6.2. Lastly, the prediction is performed. This is presented in Section 6.3. This procedure is applied to predict for the following paper properties:

- Bending stiffness MD (“KM2 Bøjstyvheth 5 grad L MV M”)
- Bending stiffness CD (“KM2 Bøjstyvheth 5 grad T MV M”)
- Curl MD (“KM2 Curl MD 50%RH MV (FMB)”)
- Curl CD (“KM2 Curl CMD 50%RH MV (FMB)”)

Figure 6.1: Overall procedure to predict a certain paper property.

The reasons why the major blocks of preprocessing, feature selection, and prediction are needed as well as the underlying theory behind each of the minor blocks is described in Chapter 3. This chapter focuses on the procedure used for this study, with Section 6.4 describing the evaluation of the prediction.

After evaluating which method, and in particular which model, performs best for curl MD, it is used to predict twist with the feature set and predictor found.

6.1. Preprocessing

The preprocessing consists of three steps:

1. Data mining
2. Data merging and manipulation
3. Multicollinearity analysis (MCA)

which are described in the following sections.

The feature selection belongs to preprocessing in the true sense of the word preprocessing. For the sake of clarity and comprehensibility, it is excluded in this section. It is described in Section 6.2.

Data mining

The data is stored in the company's database. With access via the *Wedge* [72] software and the macro stated in Appendix A, it is possible to export the data for all tags on a certain process sheet to txtfiles. Before doing so, the process sheet is created by adding all the tags resulting from the search function in *Wedge*. The search function allows to filter all process signals, called tags, by their source, tag, unit, and description.

Process sheets for this study were created with the search strings shown in Table 6.1. The “*KM2*” ensures to get only the data related to the board machine (KM) 2. Furthermore the “300” and “001”, filter values from all the measuring frames within the board machine. Therefore, it derives the value both from the middle of the web, as well as the cross-machine directional mean value. “*PE” is used to filter for values from the *PulpEye* [9], which measures fiber properties.

This results in a total of 830 tags, of which 69 are paper properties measured by the lab with the *L&W Autoline automated paper and board testing system* [8]. The remaining 761 tags will be addressed as features to apply on one of the 69 paper properties as the target in the respective model. Ultimately, this will result in 69 individual models, each predicting one paper property.

Source	Tag	Unit	Description	Quantity
		m/min	*KM2*	219
		kPa	*KM2*	134
		bar	*KM2*	64
		kW	*KM2*	25
		l/min	*KM2*	140
		rpm	*KM2*	8
		SR°	*KM2*	10
			*KM2*300*	47
			*KM2*001*	47
	3210		*PE *KM2*	67
Iggesund Lab			*KM2*	69
				830

Table 6.1: Data quantity to export found by the stated search strings.

The specified time range is 2019/11/26 – 2020/11/26. As a result, 830 txt files are generated, each containing data from one year with a frequency of one minute (60 datapoints/h · 24 h/d · 365 d = 525 600 data points). In the next step, all the txt files are merged. The final dataframe is then manipulated, which will be described in the following paragraph.

Data merging and manipulation

Merging and manipulating the data is done with the *pandas* package [71, 73]. While iterating over all txt files, *pandas* merges them. The resulting dataframe has a shape of 525 600 rows × 830 columns. Next, the target, e.g., “KM2 Bøjstyvhet 5 grad T MV M” for the bending stiffness MD, is specified. As mentioned previously, it appears that “nan” (not a number) values are present. It results from not saving values minute-wise but when a certain threshold of difference to the previously recorded value is exceeded. To handle this, following procedure is applied to the dataset: First, if a feature column, has less than 1 % non-nan values, the column is excluded, as it would be too little data. Second, all possible target columns, except the specified target column, are excluded, since they are not needed. Next, nan values in every feature column are first filled forwards if a previous not nan value exists, and then backward if not. Then, rows, where the target column has a nan value, are excluded, because those rows are useless in an algorithm. Last, the dataframe is separated into an **X** (features) and a **y** (target) set to provide data in the proper format for the algorithm. The resulting dataframe has now a shape of roughly ≈ 7500 rows × ≈ 700 columns.

For a more comprehensive explanation of this procedure, consider Table 6.2. Table 6.2a shows the initial state and Table 6.2b after the process has been run through.

x ₁	x ₂	x ₃	x ₄	x ₅	x ₆	y ₁	y ₂	y ₃
98	nan	1	nan	46	21	68	26	3
5	nan	12	nan	34	22	nan	21	5
65	nan	40	nan	12	24	nan	28	nan
45	68	1	nan	31	26	nan	29	9
7	34	nan	nan	21	22	75	24	5
85	78	8	nan	29	nan	nan	21	nan
47	36	36	45	44	nan	nan	26	3
nan	54	4	nan	18	19	nan	23	7
nan	78	24	nan	32	15	nan	24	nan
52	78	73	nan	13	nan	72	27	6
44	87	38	nan	28	nan	78	28	4

x ₁	x ₂	x ₃	x ₅	x ₆	y ₃
98	68	1	46	21	3
5	68	12	34	22	5
45	68	1	31	26	9
7	34	1	21	22	5
47	36	36	24	22	3
47	54	4	28	19	7
52	78	7	13	15	6
44	87	8	23	15	4

(a) Exemplary dataframe after merging all the txt files (shape: 11 × 9)

(b) Exemplary dataframe after manipulation (shape: 8 × 6)

Table 6.2: Exemplary data manipulation for a dataframe after merging (a) with x_{1...6} feature columns and y_{1...3} target columns (shape: 11 × 9) to a dataframe after manipulation (b) and y₃ specified as the target (shape: 8 × 6).

Furthermore, after separating the dataframe to the **X** and **y** set, the rows are shuffled randomly and each set is split into a training and a test set with a proportion of 80/20.

Before dealing with the feature selection, a multicollinearity analysis (MCA) is applied to the **X** set, pairwise computed with Spearman’s correlation coefficient.

Multicollinearity analysis (MCA)

The multicollinearity analysis (MCA) correlation is computed pairwise with Spearman’s correlation coefficient. If the correlation between column *i* and *j* is higher than a certain threshold, then column *i* is excluded from the dataset. Either 100 % or 90 % is selected as the threshold for a run. A threshold of 100 % means that effectively no column is dropped, since no column correlates to another by more than 100 %, even if the columns are identical.

6.2. Feature Selection

For feature selection, there are filters, wrappers, and embedded methods, which are presented in Section 3.2. Because of the high computational costs of wrappers, they are not examined in this study. Two filter and embedded methods each are examined. These are for filter methods: a univariate linear regression test, which computes the F score for each feature and target, and the mutual information between each feature and target. To not only rely on correlation, but consider the later used predictor, embedded methods are used. The two approaches are the recursive feature elimination (RFE) and the

recursive feature addition (RFA) method with different predictors. Only one of these is executed at a time per run and will be described in the following paragraphs.

Which of these approaches is executed depends on the selected threshold in the MCA. The RFE method is applied regardless of this threshold. The RFA method is only applied when the threshold is 100 %, as this is the only way to ensure that the initial set features are included in the data set in any case, whereas the filter method is only applied when the threshold is 90 %. This prevents multicollinearity is necessary for the reasons stated in Section 3.1. The filter methods rank the features and the top ten are selected, according to Lätti's best practice experience [55]. Therefore, in contrast to the RFE and RFA, the filter method does not need a predictor.

Regarding a later interpretation of the models, less complex predictors, such as Lasso, Ridge and Elastic Net, Linear SVR (regularized linear regression models) are examined. To make more accurate predictions, slightly more complex such as decision tree (DT), random forest (RF), and extremely randomized tree (ET) used (tree and ensemble models) are examined. Tree and ensemble models are more interpretable than deep neural networks (deep learning). For visualization of these statements, please refer to Figure 3.10. For an explanation of the predictors please refer to Section 3.3.

All methods are applied, one at a time, to the entire data set. The new \mathbf{X} set for the prediction results from the RFE, allowing to conclude of which and how many features are best to predict the target with the chosen predictor. The prediction is performed with the same predictor and with a multi-layer perceptron (MLP), with a more detailed insight in Section 6.3.

The preset features are the influencing factors mentioned in the paragraphs “Bending stiffness” and “Curl and twist” in Section 2.1.

6.3. Prediction

The prediction takes a set of features selected by the previous step. It examines the same predictors as described previously, with the addition of a multi-layer perceptron (MLP). For an explanation of the methods please refer to Section 3.3. If the feature selection was done with, e.g., a decision tree (DT), then a DT is used for the prediction as well. This logic applies to the features selected by the RFE and RFA methods. Furthermore, a prediction with an MLP is done with those features, as well as the features selected by the filter methods.

6.4. Evaluation

The evaluation of the predictions is done by computing an R^2 score, a mean absolute error (MAE), and a maximum absolute error (max. abs. error). The test dataset, which includes 20 % randomly selected

data points from the dataset after manipulation, is used to calculate the metrics. This data has never been seen by the predictor.

Also, an analysis is performed on the importance of each feature in the model using SHAP values (refer to Section 3.4 for an explanation), as well as a variability analysis.

Furthermore, an examination of the influence of the No. samples is done by gradually increasing the No. samples. For every step the R^2 score, the MAE, and the max. abs. error is plotted.

Lastly, a comparison of the different methods regarding computation time concerning the R^2 score, and No. selected features is made by measuring how long the feature selection has run.

The metrics mentioned above are described in Section 3.4.

7. Results and discussion

In this chapter, the results of the procedure described in Chapter 6 are presented and discussed. The summary and conclusion can be found in Chapter 8.

First, the results of the major blocks of Figure 6.1 are presented in Sections 7.1 to 7.3 with the outcome of which specific procedure is the best for a given paper property. Last, the results of the prediction with the best model for the examined paper properties:

- Bending stiffness MD (“KM2 Bøjstyvheth 5 grad L MV M”)
- Bending stiffness CD (“KM2 Bøjstyvheth 5 grad T MV M”)
- Curl MD (“KM2 Curl MD 50%RH MV (FMB)”)
- Curl CD (“KM2 Curl CD 50%RH MV (FMB)”)

are presented. Only stiffness MD is presented in detail, as the same outcome applies for the other properties. If not it is commented in the corresponding section. The method with the best result for curl MD is used to predict the twist (“KM2 Twist 50%RH MV (FMB)”).

Furthermore, the results of the feature importance and the sensitivity analysis are presented (Sections 7.4 and 7.5), as well as the influence of the No. samples and computation time for each method (Sections 7.6 and 7.7).

7.1. Results of the preprocessing

The result of this step is a reduction of the dataframe from a shape of 525 600 rows \times 830 columns to roughly 7400 rows for bending stiffness as target, 5600 rows for curl as target, and 712 columns for both, including the one target column. The number of rows depends on how often the certain a paper property was measured.

With the MCA the number of columns is reduced to 417 columns, including the one target column. In this case, a reduction of over 41 % was achieved, which allows the conclusion that roughly 58 % of the data is sufficient to describe KM 2’s process.

Contrary to the advantage of requiring less computation time for the subsequent feature selection, due to the smaller amount of data, and not running the risk of selecting correlating features through the filter methods, there is a major disadvantage: Features that are helpful for a later interpretation of the model may be removed. While there is nothing mathematically wrong with removing correlated features, if “grammage” is removed for “load cleaning blade”, for example, this is obstructive/hindering, since the “load cleaning blade” does not allow an interpretation on how it will affect bending stiffness, for

example. Furthermore, the RFA method, which is supposed to counteract these disadvantages, can then no longer be executed without errors.

For the reasons mentioned above, the $MCA_{100\%}$ method, i.e., no MCA in practice, is the most suitable one for preprocessing.

Discussion of the results of the preprocessing

The results show that a multicollinearity analysis (MCA) is not appropriate, since it removes features based purely on statistics, which would contribute a high value to the interpretation of the models in a later step. Care would have to be taken to preserve the *correct* feature in each case.

The simple approach of filling the nan values in every feature column first forwards and then backward does not seem to cause any problems. However, time delays, abnormal operating conditions, and outliers are not addressed. Again, this did not lead to any problems or exceedingly poor results.

7.2. Results of the feature selection

With the feature selection process setup, as stated in Figure 6.1, a total of 23 different approaches are examined (7 predictors with RFE and RFA with a previous $MCA_{100\%}$ and RFE with a previous $MCA_{90\%} + 2$ filter methods). The two filter methods cannot be evaluated at this point since they only select the ten most correlated features without using a predictor. For the other 21 approaches, using the predictor and the test set, the R^2 score is calculated. These are plotted for each target in Figure 7.1.

It can be seen that a high R^2 score is achieved for the bending stiffnesses through all predictors ($\gtrsim 0.8$ throughout all methods). If the results of the curl are added, it becomes apparent that the ET performs best ($\gtrsim 0.95$ throughout all methods).

Furthermore, it is also recognized that the $MCA_{90\%}$ does not perform better and the RFA method does not perform worse than the other RFEs with $MCA_{100\%}$. If not only the R^2 score, but also the calculation time is considered, a major advantage of the RFA method becomes clear: It is faster. Please consider Section 7.7 for details. Last, with the features not selected by the RFA method, the interpretability of the final model and thus further analysis of the process may be difficult or impossible.

It is striking that throughout all methods for the bending stiffness MD the following features are always selected: the thickness, at least one of the measured basis weights, jet-wire speed difference, moisture, and different machine speeds are selected.

When comparing the methods RFA and RFE with $MCA_{100\%}$ and RFE with $MCA_{90\%}$ with each other, it is noticeable that the previously defined initial features are always selected with the RFA method, whereas the RFE method with $MCA_{100\%}$ selects more profound features regarding interpretability.

As a result of the aforementioned reasons the RFA method (with $MCA_{100\%}$, i.e., no MCA in practice) is the most suitable method for feature selection.

Figure 7.1: Comparison of different feature selection methods for bending stiffness MD.

Discussion of the results of the feature selection

For feature selection, filters (univariate linear regression test and mutual information), and embedded methods (recursive feature elimination (RFE) and recursive feature addition (RFA) with different predictors) were evaluated. The results show that embedded methods are preferable to filters because they are not only based on statistics but also take into account the predictor to be used. Moreover, they make an autonomous selection (the smallest feature set with the highest R^2 score) whereas the filters rank and select a number determined by the user.

Between selecting RFE or RFA, the RFA method should be chosen. However, it is a prerequisite that domain knowledge is available. In any case, the feature set selected by this method contains the features that allow a later interpretation and then adds other features that improve the R^2 score. If no domain knowledge is available, the RFE method is suitable to get a good impression of which features have an influence on the target in the process. Of the various predictors, the Linear SVR in combination with RFE is not to be preferred, since it always yielded the worst result. For this task with this dataset, the extremely randomized tree (ET) seems to be the best. With the RFA method, on the other hand, a similarly good result was achieved with each predictor.

7.3. Results of the prediction

In this section, the results of the predictions on each of the targets are presented, but at first two generalities are found.

Running the prediction with an MLP does not have much advantage, as it does not produce significantly better results as the R^2 score. Prediction with an MLP on the contrary, represents another process step, thus more computation time. Furthermore, MLPs are worse in terms of interpretability than all other predictors studied in this paper (see Figure 3.10).

Running the prediction with the same predictor as in the feature selection process for a second time is not necessary. Therefore, the results of the predictions with all predictors for the features selected by the filter methods, as well as the predictions with an MLP for all feature selection methods are presented in Tables E.10 to E.12 in Appendix E.

Tables 7.1 to 7.3 show the R^2 score, max. abs. error, and MAE for the predictions with the feature selection methods from Figure 7.1 in a value range from 7 to 100 mN m. It can be seen that the Linear SVR performs significantly worse than the other predictors for the RFE methods, and it also performs worse in the RFA method. Consistently good results are provided by the decision tree-based methods, ET leading the way.

The corresponding results for the other examined properties can be found in Appendices B to D.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFE with Ridge and MCA ₁₀₀ %	0.9268	59.65 mN m	3.87 mN m
RFE with RF and MCA ₁₀₀ %	0.9947	19.56 mN m	0.99 mN m
RFE with Linear SVR and MCA ₁₀₀ %	0.8669	28.12 mN m	5.41 mN m
RFE with Lasso and MCA ₁₀₀ %	0.9754	13.69 mN m	2.45 mN m
RFE with ET and MCA ₁₀₀ %	0.9968	10.54 mN m	0.81 mN m
RFE with Elastic Net and MCA ₁₀₀ %	0.9842	11.06 mN m	1.97 mN m
RFE with DT and MCA ₁₀₀ %	0.9914	23.06 mN m	1.19 mN m

Table 7.1: Results of the prediction for bending stiffness MD with RFE and MCA₁₀₀ % methods.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFE with Ridge and MCA ₉₀ %	0.8809	68.25 mN m	4.42 mN m
RFE with RF and MCA ₉₀ %	0.9926	21.69 mN m	1.15 mN m
RFE with Linear SVR and MCA ₉₀ %	0.5841	128.28 mN m	9.40 mN m
RFE with Lasso and MCA ₉₀ %	0.9737	13.91 mN m	2.56 mN m
RFE with ET and MCA ₉₀ %	0.9957	16.71 mN m	0.84 mN m
RFE with Elastic Net and MCA ₉₀ %	0.9768	13.95 mN m	2.39 mN m
RFE with DT and MCA ₉₀ %	0.9806	43.22 mN m	1.58 mN m

Table 7.2: Results of the prediction for bending stiffness MD with RFE and MCA₉₀ % methods.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFA with Ridge	0.9759	17.00 mN m	2.46 mN m
RFA with RF	0.9941	23.86 mN m	1.03 mN m
RFA with Linear SVR	0.9491	31.83 mN m	3.48 mN m
RFA with Lasso	0.9649	33.03 mN m	2.85 mN m
RFA with ET	0.9969	11.44 mN m	0.79 mN m
RFA with Elastic Net	0.9658	30.72 mN m	2.83 mN m
RFA with DT	0.9939	17.14 mN m	1.09 mN m

Table 7.3: Results of the prediction for bending stiffness MD with RFA methods.

Table 7.4 shows the result for each of the studied features using the feature selection method of an RFA with ET and prediction with the ET.

Target	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE	value range
Bending stiffness MD	0.9969	11.44 mN m	0.79 mN m	7 to 100 mN m
Bending stiffness CD	0.9853	34.87 mN m	0.46 mN m	5 to 45 mN m
Curl MD	0.9629	1.07 m^{-1}	0.05 m^{-1}	-1 to 1 m^{-1}
Curl CD	0.9244	2.81 m^{-1}	0.14 m^{-1}	-1 to 3 m^{-1}

Table 7.4: Results for bending stiffness/curl with the feature selection method of an RFA with ET and prediction with the ET.

Figure 7.2 shows the MAE, computed standard deviations from the lab in comparison to the prediction, as well as the max. abs. error for a grammage of $\{180, 190, \dots, 400\} \text{ g/m}^2$ with an interval of $\pm 5 \text{ g/m}^2$ for the predicted bending stiffness MD with RFA with ET as the predictor, as this appears to be the best method from the examined. Attention should be paid more to the MAE, rather than to the max. abs. error. It can be seen that the MAE increases with a higher basis weight. One possible reason for this could be the data distribution: there are fewer examples for the higher basis weights (see Figures 2.4 and 2.6), resulting in poorer predictions.

In addition, a Durbin–Watson test is performed for this method with a result of $d = 1.32$. Since $1 < d < 3$ the presence of autocorrelation at lag 1 in the residuals can be discarded.

Lastly, in Figure 7.3 the prediction of bending stiffness MD with RFA and ET as the predictor is plotted as a time series for a random date. Instead of the actual prediction, the moving average of the prediction (average of the last 10 min) should be considered and it should be noted that the perfectly predicted values may be values that are included in the training set, so that the model knows them perfectly (by memory). It can be seen, that in general the prediction follows the actual values measured by the lab. In terms of a practical application: The area marked in blue shows a time range in which the bending stiffness has decreased. Since the next measurement is only ≈ 45 min later, the machine operator only notices this change then. With a prediction like this, the machine operator could have already reacted to this change after a few minutes and therefore counteract the effect.

Figure 7.2: Metric plot for bending stiffness MD with RFA with ET as the predictor.

Figure 7.3: Prediction of bending stiffness MD with RFA with ET as the predictor for a random day.

(a) Prediction of curl MD with RFA with ET as the predictor for a randomly chosen day

(b) Prediction of twist with RFA with ET as the predictor for a randomly chosen day

Figure 7.4: Comparison of the predictions of curl MD and twist with the same feature set and method.

Discussion of the results of the prediction

Most of the predictions are quite good. These are slightly better than the MSEs achieved for the curl by Bortolin et al. in *On modelling of curl in multi-ply paperboard* in 2006 (following values are converted to RMSEs to be compared to the achieved MAEs): 0.35 m^{-1} vs. 0.05 m^{-1} for curl MD and 0.13 m^{-1} vs. 0.14 m^{-1} for curl CD, where always “result of [66]” vs. “achieved in this study” applies.

A generally found observation is that the predictions get worse for higher basis weights (see Figure 7.2). The simple reason for this is that it is underrepresented in the dataset (see Figures 2.4 and 2.6), or that the process is different for higher levels of bending stiffness/curl. However, if the importance is placed more on the trend of the prediction and less on the absolute number, this procedure is very useful, as shown in Figure 7.3. A drop in bending stiffness can be detected before the next laboratory measurement and the operator can counteract it at an early stage.

Results and discussion of the prediction of twist

The best model (ET) is used to predict the twist. The feature set is the same as the one for curl MD. The model achieves an R^2 score of 0.2755, max. abs. error of 5.22 m^{-1} , and an MAE of 0.10 m^{-1} (in a value range from -1 to 1 m^{-1}). In contrast to the prediction of the curl MD, this result is fairly bad: R^2 score of 0.9629, max. abs. error of 1.07 m^{-1} , and an MAE of 0.05 m^{-1} (in a value range from -1 to 1 m^{-1}). An illustration of this comparison is given in Figure 7.4.

This shows how important it is to choose the *correct* features. The feature set contains mainly features of mean values of the process/paperboard (flows to headbox, mean basis weights, mean thicknesses, temperatures in the dryer section). These “global” features are relevant to the curl, but not to the twist since this is a very “local” property [74].

7.4. Results of the feature importance

Figure 7.5 shows the result of the top five features, regarding their importance, for bending stiffness MD with RFA with ET as the predictor. These are: thickness (“Tjocklek”) (measured just before the pope), speed of a pulling roll (“Hastighet dragverk”), basis weight (“Ytvikt”) (measured just before the pope), speed of the tambour (“Tamburhastighet”), and pressure headbox center (“Tryck mäld innloplåda center”).

The calculated SHAP value indicates how large the impact of the respective feature is on the model output. The higher the absolute value, the greater the influence of the feature on the property. A positive value indicates that the output is influenced towards higher numbers and vice versa. Furthermore, the color scaling of the feature values, i.e., the actual value of the feature, blue for low feature value, and red for high feature value, shows whether rather low or high values of the respective feature have a positive or negative influence. Finally, the height of the respective feature value indicates how many features are present with this feature value.

It can be seen, that a greater thickness and basis weight contribute to a higher bending stiffness MD, whereas the speed of a pulling roll, speed of the tambour, and pressure headbox center contribute to a lower bending stiffness MD. This result is expected, as the thickness and basis weight have a direct physical impact on the bending stiffness (see paragraph “Bending stiffness” in Section 2.1). The influence of the other three features can be explained as follows: If paperboard with a higher basis weight is produced, it will be produced at a lower speed. A lower speed is therefore merely the consequence of higher basis weight. As a result of the lower machine speed, the pressure in the headbox is also lower, since the jet also exits at a lower speed.

Figure 7.5: Feature importance of bending stiffness MD (SHAP values) with RFA with ET as the predictor.

7.5. Results of the variability analysis

Figure 7.6 shows the result of the sensitivity analysis for the bending stiffness MD with RFA with ET as the predictor. At this stage, three out of the top five features are varying. It can be seen, that for the combination of basis weight, thickness, and the tambour speed/speed of a pulling roll, the predicted time series starts to variate, as well as the actual values do.

This result is expected since each feature in those combinations of three out of the top five features has the highest impact on the model output ($5 < |\text{SHAP value}| < 10$).

For the curl, the identified features are the refining energy to the long-fiber, water to the liquid application system, and pressure in the drying cylinder (group 10, bottom).

Figure 7.6: Sensitivity analysis for bending stiffness MD with RFA with ET as the predictor.

7.6. Influence of the number of samples

In this section, the influence of the number of (No.) samples is examined. From Figure 7.7 it can be seen that for the bending stiffness MD, a small number of samples, ≈ 400 samples, is already sufficient for a fairly good prediction: R^2 score of ≈ 0.99 , MAE of ≈ 1.28 mN m (in a value range from 7 to 100 mN m), and even with a smaller amount of samples of 200 samples, an R^2 score of ≈ 0.98 , and an MAE of ≈ 2 mN m is still achieved. This applies to the bending stiffness MD and, with an R^2 score lower by 0.01 and an MAE of ≈ 1 mN m (in a value range from 5 to 45 mN m), also to the bending stiffness CD. In contrast, Figure 7.8 shows the need for more samples (≈ 1200 samples) to achieve an R^2 score of ≈ 0.9 and an MAE of ≈ 0.08 m $^{-1}$ (in a value range from -1 to 1 m $^{-1}$) for the curl MD, whereas for curl CD ≈ 3300 samples are needed to achieve the same result (in a value range from -1 to 3 m $^{-1}$).

These results confirm Lätti's and Wenzel's best practice experience that 6 to 12 months of data is initially sufficient to set up such models [55, 75].

Figure 7.7: Influence of the No. samples on the metric for the prediction of bending stiffness MD with RFA with ET as the predictor.

Figure 7.8: Influence of the No. samples on the metric for the prediction of curl MD with RFE with ET as the predictor.

7.7. Computation time and number of selected features

In this section, the computation time concerning the R^2 score, and No. selected features for bending stiffness MD is examined. Table 7.5 shows the comparison of the different methods regarding computation time, R^2 score, and No. selected features for bending stiffness MD (results for the other examined properties are similar). All calculations were run on an Intel i7-7500U CPU @ 2.70 GHz with 16 GB RAM.

First of all, it can be seen that the filter methods are fast, especially the univariate linear regression test which computes the F score (0.07 s), but they do not select features rather than rank them. As they do not consider a model, but just rely on correlations, no R^2 score can be computed. In contrast to this, the RFE and RFA methods use a certain predictor, so the No. selected features lead to the highest R^2 score for this certain predictor.

Furthermore, it is shown that the RFE with $MCA_{100\%}$ methods have the highest computation time with ≈ 4 h on average, whereas the RFE with $MCA_{90\%}$ methods needs ≈ 2 h on average and the RFA methods the lowest with ≈ 2 min on average. Moreover, the RFA methods are the only ones that scores through all predictors an R^2 score ≥ 0.96 .

Regarding the No. selected features from the perspective of interpretation, $\gtrsim 30$ features have a negative effect, as a number that high does not allow to conclude the contribution of the individual features to the model's output. Additionally, such models exhibit higher complexibility and are therefore harder to understand. However, if the No. selected features is rather low ($\lesssim 5$), the selected features might not allow an explanation of the model's output from a physical point of view, as these features tend to rely on each other only on a correlational level.

Lastly, if the actual selected features are considered, it is striking that the features selected by the RFE methods often contain some features, which do not allow a comprehensive explanation of the model, as these features do not have a physical impact but only correlate to the bending stiffness MD. This contributes to the advantage of the RFA methods which have a predefined set of features that relies on physical relations to the certain paper property with the result of an explainable model.

Method	computation time	R^2 score	No. selected features
Filter (mutual information)	2 min	–	all
Filter (F score)	0.07 s	–	all
RFE with MCA ₁₀₀ % with Lasso	1.12 h	0.9754	9
RFE with MCA ₁₀₀ % with Elastic Net	1.17 h	0.9842	26
RFE with MCA ₁₀₀ % with Ridge	3.22 min	0.9268	10
RFE with MCA ₁₀₀ % with Lasso SVR	4.05 h	0.8669	1
RFE with MCA ₁₀₀ % with DT	1.43 h	0.9914	8
RFE with MCA ₁₀₀ % with RF	1.81 h	0.9947	49
RFE with MCA ₁₀₀ % with ET	20.8 h	0.9968	44
RFE with MCA ₉₀ % with Lasso	32.9 min	0.9737	45
RFE with MCA ₉₀ % with Elastic Net	32.17 min	0.9768	74
RFE with MCA ₉₀ % with Ridge	58.02 s	0.8809	6
RFE with MCA ₉₀ % with Linear SVR	1.61 h	0.5841	6
RFE with MCA ₉₀ % with DT	32.95 min	0.9806	4
RFE with MCA ₉₀ % with RF	55.97 min	0.9926	11
RFE with MCA ₉₀ % with ET	6.94 h	0.9957	163
RFA with Lasso	32 s	0.9649	27
RFA with Elastic Net	34 s	0.9658	27
RFA with Ridge	3 s	0.9759	27
RFA with Linear SVR	4 min	0.9491	26
RFA with DT	40 s	0.9939	18
RFA with RF	42 s	0.9941	23
RFA with ET	8 min	0.9969	26

Table 7.5: Comparison of the different methods regarding computation time with respect to R^2 score, and No. selected features for bending stiffness MD run on an Intel i7-7500U CPU @ 2.70 GHz with 16 GB RAM.

8. Conclusion and outlook

In this study, the applicability and accuracy of various machine learning (ML) methods for predicting paperboard properties based on raw material and process data were investigated. Determining the possibilities of ML, a systematical evaluation about bending stiffness and curl in machine direction (MD) and cross-machine direction (CD) was developed. The focus was on the feature selection. Moreover, for the selection of the best model, mainly the interpretability was considered besides the computation time, R^2 score (coefficient of determination), maximum absolute error (max. abs. error), and mean absolute error (MAE). The one-year database from *Iggesunds Bruk's* KM 2 with a time resolution of ≈ 45 min for the production of all the different grades has proven to be a sufficient amount of data.

The preprocessing, feature selection, and prediction procedure presented in this study is modular and automatically evaluates different approaches/predictors in the respective process steps. The structure of the procedure is recommended as it is. The respective code can be found at [1].

Neither feature scaling (e.g., standardizing) nor outlier detection was performed in this study. Those could be investigated in future studies to achieve a cleaner data set. An outlier detection demonstrably improves the performance [66]. Furthermore, abnormal operating conditions can be removed, e.g., directly after a start-up. Time delays between features were not considered in this study since they are either paperboard machine parameters or supply system parameters, so there is no critical need to consider them [55].

For the feature selection, the recursive feature addition (RFA) method with the ET performs best for the given data set. The RFA requires less computation time compared to the recursive feature elimination (RFE) method, which allows setting up models more quickly. Besides, this method ensures that certain features specified by the modeler are within the feature set.

The scorer used in this study is the R^2 score. Strictly speaking, this is the unadjusted R^2 score. A suggestion for future studies is to use a modified version, the adjusted R^2 score. It considers the number of features, therefore, penalizing the addition of unnecessary features. Furthermore, models with different numbers of features are comparable. In general, the adjusted R^2 score will only increase if the addition of a new feature produces a large enough reduction in the residual sum of squares. [30, 76]

Specifying the metric for a product/grade is a recommendation for the evaluation. It could provide a better insight into the error than the evaluation of the whole data set. For this purpose, the data set would have to be extended by the “product” column in advance. This new feature could also be interesting as model input since the different products have different specifications in terms of the properties. Therefore, the process conditions are adjusted. It is conceivable that it could predict the general level of a property. Furthermore, feature engineering is applicable. The data set could be extended by the density (basis weight per thickness), draws (differences in speed), and coating grammages/thicknesses (differences in grammage/thickness), to name but a few.

The feature importance analysis was conducted with Shapley additive explanation (SHAP) values. These give a quick insight into which features have an influence on the model's output and in which way, making it a proper tool for the feature analysis.

The sensitivity analysis identifies which features introduce variability into the process. These are the combination of basis weight, thickness, and tambour speed for the bending stiffness; refining energy to the long-fiber, water to the liquid application system, and pressure in the drying cylinder (group 10, bottom) for the curl. The approach of simply freezing all but the five most important features to a fixed value and set only these five in different combinations to their original values is not efficient. In short, it only proves that the most important features are indeed important. A suggestion for improvement would be to correlate the residuals of the prediction with the features. Another suggestion is to use Spearman's correlation coefficient to correlate each feature with the target. Spearman's is less sensitive to outliers. To use Pearson's correlation coefficient, the data set has to be clean, i.e., absence of outliers [77]. Lastly, restricting the number of features to have one feature impacting the model's output more distinguishable from another is recommended. To end up with, e.g., ≈ 15 features as suggested by Lätti [55], the feature set could either be merely the previously determined features from a domain expert and or running a downstream screening that leaves only those features in the set that seem reasonable.

In this study, only the CD-mean values of the properties were used. Therefore, the CD-mean values of bending stiffness MD/CD, curl MD/CD, and twist were predicted. For a prediction of the paperboard properties at the different CD positions, the presented procedure is employable in changing the model's input to the respective CD measurements.

Overall, ML methods are powerful, and the different models, fed with the *correct* features, achieve good results. The feature selection is crucial for the quality of the prediction. Nevertheless, it requires domain knowledge to ensure that the model is reliable, comprehensible, and interpretable.

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Appendix

A. *Wedge* code to export data from *Wedge*

This code is inserted and executed as a macro. Thanks to Mika Soujarv from the *Wedge* support team for providing the code.

```
(setq i 0)
(mapcar (lambda (n)
  (if (node:could-have-data? n)
    (progn (ascii-save:do-save (list n)
      (concatenate "C:/tmp/measdata" (print i t) ".txt")
      ",")
      (quote col-1-time)
    )
    (setq i (+ i 1))
  )))
(graph:get-nodes *graph*)
)
```

B. Results of the prediction for bending stiffness CD

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFE with Ridge and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.9663	35.21 mN m	1.05 mN m
RFE with RF and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.9826	34.93 mN m	0.55 mN m
RFE with Linear SVR and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.9071	32.28 mN m	2.10 mN m
RFE with Lasso and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.9702	34.47 mN m	0.97 mN m
RFE with ET and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.9855	34.59 mN m	0.46 mN m
RFE with Elastic Net and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.9623	33.97 mN m	1.10 mN m
RFE with DT and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.9799	35.90 mN m	0.64 mN m

Table B.1: Results of the prediction for bending stiffness CD with RFE and $MCA_{100\%}$ methods.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFE with Ridge and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.8795	32.09 mN m	1.95 mN m
RFE with RF and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.9766	35.61 mN m	0.61 mN m
RFE with Linear SVR and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.7943	32.71 mN m	2.89 mN m
RFE with Lasso and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.9575	33.71 mN m	1.19 mN m
RFE with ET and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.9842	35.30 mN m	0.48 mN m
RFE with Elastic Net and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.9063	35.49 mN m	1.93 mN m
RFE with DT and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.9740	35.90 mN m	0.71 mN m

Table B.2: Results of the prediction for bending stiffness MD with RFE and $MCA_{90\%}$ methods.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFA with Ridge	0.9674	34.50 mN m	1.04 mN m
RFA with RF	0.9822	36.08 mN m	0.54 mN m
RFA with Linear SVR	0.9433	34.62 mN m	1.53 mN m
RFA with Lasso	0.9543	34.73 mN m	1.21 mN m
RFA with ET	0.9853	34.87 mN m	0.46 mN m
RFA with Elastic Net	0.9557	34.82 mN m	1.19 mN m
RFA with DT	0.9811	33.07 mN m	0.63 mN m

Table B.3: Results of the prediction for bending stiffness CD with RFA methods.

C. Results of the prediction for curl MD

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFE with Ridge and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.1004	2.19 m^{-1}	0.25 m^{-1}
RFE with RF and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.9087	1.27 m^{-1}	0.08 m^{-1}
RFE with Linear SVR and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.0141	2.21 m^{-1}	0.30 m^{-1}
RFE with Lasso and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.5348	1.58 m^{-1}	0.20 m^{-1}
RFE with ET and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.9629	1.07 m^{-1}	0.05 m^{-1}
RFE with Elastic Net and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.5084	1.57 m^{-1}	0.21 m^{-1}
RFE with DT and $MCA_{100\%}$	0.7793	2.41 m^{-1}	0.11 m^{-1}

Table C.4: Results of the prediction for curl MD with RFE and $MCA_{100\%}$ methods.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFE with Ridge and MCA _{90%}	0.1004	2.20 m ⁻¹	0.25 m ⁻¹
RFE with RF and MCA _{90%}	0.8989	0.89 m ⁻¹	0.09 m ⁻¹
RFE with Linear SVR and MCA _{90%}	0.1368	2.25 m ⁻¹	0.23 m ⁻¹
RFE with Lasso and MCA _{90%}	0.4568	1.72 m ⁻¹	0.22 m ⁻¹
RFE with ET and MCA _{90%}	0.9618	1.12 m ⁻¹	0.05 m ⁻¹
RFE with Elastic Net and MCA _{90%}	0.4404	1.70 m ⁻¹	0.23 m ⁻¹
RFE with DT and MCA _{90%}	0.7828	2.83 m ⁻¹	0.09 m ⁻¹

Table C.5: Results of the prediction for curl MD with RFE and MCA_{90%} methods.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFA with Ridge	0.6800	1.19 m ⁻¹	0.18 m ⁻¹
RFA with RF	0.8943	1.00 m ⁻¹	0.09 m ⁻¹
RFA with Linear SVR	0.5662	1.25 m ⁻¹	0.22 m ⁻¹
RFA with Lasso	0.4860	1.65 m ⁻¹	0.21 m ⁻¹
RFA with ET	0.9569	1.16 m ⁻¹	0.06 m ⁻¹
RFA with Elastic Net	0.5080	1.55 m ⁻¹	0.21 m ⁻¹
RFA with DT	0.8959	1.33 m ⁻¹	0.08 m ⁻¹

Table C.6: Results of the prediction for curl MD with RFA methods.

D. Results of the prediction for curl CD

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFE with Ridge and MCA _{100%}	0.0082	10.02 m ⁻¹	0.58 m ⁻¹
RFE with RF and MCA _{100%}	0.7968	6.37 m ⁻¹	0.22 m ⁻¹
RFE with Linear SVR and MCA _{100%}	0.0	8.25 m ⁻¹	0.83 m ⁻¹
RFE with Lasso and MCA _{100%}	0.3077	7.42 m ⁻¹	0.47 m ⁻¹
RFE with ET and MCA _{100%}	0.9244	2.81 m ⁻¹	0.14 m ⁻¹
RFE with Elastic Net and MCA _{100%}	0.4273	6.63 m ⁻¹	0.44 m ⁻¹
RFE with DT and MCA _{100%}	0.8042	3.99 m ⁻¹	0.23 m ⁻¹

Table D.7: Results of the prediction for curl CD with RFE and MCA_{100%} methods.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFE with Ridge and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.4539	7.01 m^{-1}	0.46 m^{-1}
RFE with RF and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.7987	4.24 m^{-1}	0.23 m^{-1}
RFE with Linear SVR and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.2653	8.77 m^{-1}	0.51 m^{-1}
RFE with Lasso and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.1912	8.13 m^{-1}	0.55 m^{-1}
RFE with ET and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.9243	3.18 m^{-1}	0.14 m^{-1}
RFE with Elastic Net and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.4727	6.64 m^{-1}	0.43 m^{-1}
RFE with DT and $MCA_{90\%}$	0.7025	7.66 m^{-1}	0.24 m^{-1}

Table D.8: Results of the prediction for curl CD with RFE and $MCA_{90\%}$ methods.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	max. abs. error	MAE
RFA with Ridge	0.5459	7.51 m^{-1}	0.41 m^{-1}
RFA with RF	0.8099	3.63 m^{-1}	0.23 m^{-1}
RFA with Linear SVR	0.3085	7.67 m^{-1}	0.56 m^{-1}
RFA with Lasso	0.1994	9.15 m^{-1}	0.52 m^{-1}
RFA with ET	0.9086	2.94 m^{-1}	0.15 m^{-1}
RFA with Elastic Net	0.3188	8.68 m^{-1}	0.49 m^{-1}
RFA with DT	0.8038	3.54 m^{-1}	0.24 m^{-1}

Table D.9: Results of the prediction for curl CD with RFA methods.

E. Results of the prediction with an MLP for bending stiffness MD

Feature selection method	R^2 score	RMSE	MAE
RFE with Ridge	0.9449	4.83 mN m	3.19 mN m
RFE with Linear SVR	0.8717	7.37 mN m	5.47 mN m
RFE with Lasso	0.9871	2.34 mN m	1.74 mN m
RFE with ET	0.9919	1.85 mN m	1.37 mN m
RFE with Elastic Net	0.9897	2.08 mN m	1.62 mN m
Mutual information	0.9557	4.33 mN m	2.81 mN m
Univariate linear regression test	0.5567	13.71 mN m	11.59 mN m

Table E.10: Results of the regression from an MLP for bending stiffness MD with $MCA_{100\%}$.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	RMSE	MAE
RFE with Ridge	0.8965	6.62 mN m	4.32 mN m
RFE with RF	0.9907	1.99 mN m	1.42 mN m
RFE with Linear SVR	0.6145	12.78 mN m	9.05 mN m
RFE with Lasso	0.9890	2.16 mN m	1.52 mN m
RFE with ET	0.9906	1.99 mN m	1.43 mN m
RFE with Elastic Net	0.9917	1.88 mN m	1.42 mN m
RFE with DT	0.9119	6.11 mN m	4.39 mN m
Mutual information	0.9652	3.84 mN m	2.59 mN m
Univariate linear regression test	0.9192	5.85 mN m	4.12 mN m

Table E.11: Results of the regression from an MLP for bending stiffness MD with $MCA_{90\%}$.

Feature selection method	R^2 score	RMSE	MAE
RFA with Ridge	0.9887	2.19 mN m	1.67 mN m
RFA with RF	0.9875	2.29 mN m	1.73 mN m
RFA with Linear SVR	0.9879	2.26 mN m	1.69 mN m
RFA with Lasso	0.9829	2.69 mN m	2.02 mN m
RFA with ET	0.9774	3.09 mN m	2.33 mN m
RFA with Elastic Net	0.9896	2.10 mN m	1.59 mN m
RFA with DT	0.9873	2.32 mN m	1.72 mN m
Mutual information	0.9658	3.81 mN m	2.62 mN m
Univariate linear regression test	0.9610	4.07 mN m	2.62 mN m

Table E.12: Results of the prediction from an MLP for bending stiffness MD with RFA.